

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
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 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)

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Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 23 June 2025.

Keynote of the case letter

University grants commission (UGC) is a central representative of Bangladeshi universities. UGC controls the higher education quality, research, publication, teaching, learning, PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) training, Postdoctoral training, professor training, professor assessment, and academic promotion policy of Bangladesh government. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is asking the legal aid support of united nations (UN), Bangladesh government, and Australian government through Professor Dr. Syed Muhammed Abul Faiz, chairman, UGC, Bangladesh. Therefore, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is approaching to Professor Dr. SMA Faiz, Chairman, UGC to enhance higher education support in Bangladesh. PhD is a process of life-long journey of self-investment, self-dedication, and knowledge creation for the peace of human being. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is officially submitting an Australian Post-doctoral answer script, Australian PhD answer script, Australian Post-doctoral thesis and/or Nobel prize thesis, Australian PhD thesis and/or Nobel prize thesis, Australian PhD research, Australian Post-doctoral research, Australian PhD publication, PhD harassment, PhD tragedy, and report of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school to the Chairman, director, and secretary of UGC; Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain remarked about private university harassment in his self-professional climbing in Bangladesh. He is also asking the exact solution, self-surviving and safety support as a scientist or a PhD consultant or a distinguished professor or an educationist or a renowned textile engineer. He is asking national and international assessment to satisfy national and international research protocol on behalf of Bangladesh government. If possible, if it can be knocked to Australian

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government, if it can be included to Australian government in the assessment process. He is also approaching zero crime prospects for the excellency of university education and global surviving. The whole explanation of this case letter is a practical approach and research proposal for a quality higher education and research for global development in higher education. Both Bangladesh and Australian government may continue the investigation of life-threatening conspiracy for the future protection of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain and/or relevant scientists under the service of specialized and ethical team under the funding of Australian government and/or Bangladesh government. A specialized team may be formed by the support of Indian UGC, Bangladeshi UGC, government of China, government of Australia, government of United Kingdom, government of United States of America, Government of Russia, etc. What should be the reason to kill a PhD scientist in a PhD school? It is necessary to find out the exact reason to continue the system of international PhD schooling. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to propose to be a chancellor or vice chancellor of top reputed universities or technological universities in national and international platform. Ethics is the glory of higher education. Education glorifies the human brain. Concern authorities may prove that investment in education is the best investment to enhance ethical standard to ensure zero crime policy to make a criminal free world. Therefore, PhD in PhD and Post doctorate in PhD have been narrated to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain claimed doctoral and post-doctoral thesis in Australia. In general, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is begging and requesting to extend an official support of Bangladesh government, Australian government, and UN. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get a legal support of Bangladesh government to get PhD compensation award of 230,72,50,000AUD of Australian government and death penalty of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now; scholarship of 93, 780AUD + compensation award of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87, 560 AUD (in words: one lakh eighty-seven thousand five hundred and sixty AUD only). He is asking a compensation of double value of PhD scholarship due to PhD harassment, quality of life harassment, and creating an artificial food crisis and marriage life/sex life harassment to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 6 July 2022 to still now. 'Education compensation award' of City University, Bangladesh (standard salary of 63,72,463BDT + compensation of double salary = 12,744,926BDT) is approached by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in term of demotion of previous designation/three public university experiences during appointment, non-standard salary, non-paid salary of study leave duration, and demotivation to PhD research in Australia. The total non-paid salary of City University, Bangladesh is 63,72,463BDT, in words: sixty-three lakh seventy-two thousand four hundred and sixty-three BDT only. The total non-paid

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compensation of City University, Bangladesh is 12,744,926BDT, in words: one crore twenty-seven lakh fourty four thousand nine hundred and twenty-six BDT only. This letter of proceeding is an appeal to the professor court and/or high court of Australia and Bangladesh.

Proposal of legal act and/or outcomes of the case study and crime analysis

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is proposing international education act to enhance higher education and research support

- a. Life time imprisonment or death penalty for the punishment of PhD conspiracy.
- b. Life time imprisonment for the punishment of promotion conspiracy/administrative conspiracy and professor trapping in any organization.
- c. Life time imprisonment for the punishment of harassing in job assessment in the name of private university graduate in Bangladesh.
- d. Life time imprisonment for the punishment for asking/showing the attitude of additional benefit from colleague for arranging, assessing, and approving university promotion.
- e. Compensation of double salary of standard salary for approving non-paid study leave and artificial demotivation, discrimination, and harassment to PhD researcher.
- f. Compensation of double salary of standard salary for approving/acting demotion of public university designation, public university experience/private university experience, artificial demotivation, artificial discrimination, and harassment to university teacher for academic and professional growth.
- g. International standard professional income support to PhD victim rather than the lower paid PhD scholarship.
- h. Additional study hours allowance to PhD victim rather than the lower paid PhD scholarship.
- i. International standard allowance to PhD victim rather than the lower paid PhD scholarship.
- j. International standard legal aid support to PhD victim and/or university victim.

Allegation to the professor court to the UGC, Bangladesh to the ministry of education, Bangladesh

- ✓ Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking recommendation and action and support to receive achieved money/earned money and compensation RMIT University, Australia (1,87,560AUD), and Australian government

(230,72,50,000AUD) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j, 2024k, 2024x; Hossain, 2025b).

- ✓ Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking recommendation and action and support to receive achieved money/earned money and education compensation award of 12, 744,926BDT (in words: one crore twenty seven lakh fourty four thousand nine hundred and twenty six BDT only) from City University of Bangladesh government (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g, 2023ah, 2023bz, 2023ca; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).
- ✓ Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking a Bangladeshi gazette of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) at the office of UGC, Bangladesh and/or ministry of education of Bangladesh government (M. A. Hossain, 2023b, 2023f, 2023g, 2023ah, 2023br; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).
- ✓ Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking action and support and funding to the relevant organization of Bangladesh, Australia, and united nations.
- ✓ Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking protection against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye to the relevant organization of Bangladesh, Australia, and united nations.
- ✓ Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking a nomination of ethical vice chancellor of Bangladesh government. In which way, chairman of trustee board and/or political professor and/or political concern should not make any unethical approach/threaten to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.).
- ✓ Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking a safety recommendation of professor board/professor court of UGC of Bangladesh government (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc; M. A. Hossain, 2023b; M. A. Hossain, 2023bw; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025b).

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1. Non-paid full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93, 780AUD + compensation of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87, 560 AUD)

2. 'PhD compensation award' of 230,72,50,000AUD of Australian government

3. Death penalty of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, RMIT University, Australia

Reasons

Life-threatening conspiracy, PhD conspiracy, quality of life harassment, creating an artificial food crisis, and marriage life/sex life harassment

- Seeking support to UGC of Bangladesh
- Seeking support to legal aid of Australia & Bangladesh
- Seeking support to legal aid of United Nations
- Seeking support to prime minister/president of Australia & Bangladesh
- Seeking support to vice chancellor and chancellor of RMIT University
- Seeking support to foreign ministry and education ministry of Australia and Bangladesh
- Seeking support to chief advisor of Bangladesh government

'Education compensation award' of City University, Bangladesh (standard salary of 63, 72, 463BDT + compensation of double salary = 12, 744,926BDT)

Reasons

Demotion of previous designation/dishonored three public university experiences during appointment, non-standard salary, non-paid salary of study leave duration, and demotivation to PhD research in Australia

- Seeking support to UGC, Bangladesh
- Seeking support to vice chancellor and vhanccellor of City University, Bangladesh
- Seeking support to legal aid of Bangladesh
- Seeking support to education ministry of Bangladesh
- Seeking support to chief advisor of Bangladesh government
- Seeking support to prime minister/president of Bangladesh

Keywords

Higher education, PhD, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.), Bangladesh, Australia

Page | 6

Letter of proceeding of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) to Bangladesh government through UGC of Bangladesh government

Date 23 June 2025

To

Professor Dr. Syed Muhammed Abul Faiz

Chairman

University Grants Commission (UGC), The People's Republic of Bangladesh

Plot#E-18/A, Agargaon Administrative Area, Sher-e-Bangla Nagar, Dhaka-1207

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Director

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Dear Chairman and Director,

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/vice chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer of prestigious university/research organization.

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Your honour for your service and contribution to the Bangladesh higher education, and research.

Your honour for your central administrative leading of higher education on behalf of Bangladesh government.

On 4 February 2025, I, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist completed five years duration full-time PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) candidature and full-time PhD practice under life-threatening conspiracy, PhD conspiracy, and official PhD harassment (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024m). Since 2022, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent few letters to UGC for the kind attention (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent cc letters and e-mail to the office of UGC. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain physically visited the office of UGC on 4 February 2025, self-funded by Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. PS (personal secretary) to UGC chairman told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “thirty vice chancellors are waiting to meet with the chairman, we are busy with the issue of Titumir college, chairman is in meeting, you didn’t get scholarship through UGC. So, this is your personal matter (M. A. Hossain, 2023ah). You may meet with a member of UGC. You may talk with the director office.” 4 February 2025, assistant director or personal secretary to director office, UGC asked and interviewed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “from where did you graduate (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)? You may have a forwarding letter (one to two pages) to the director, UGC. If we need to answer the letter, we will notify you accordingly.” Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted a copy of cc letter/e-mail letter to the assistant director (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also asked to assistant director if there is any member, UGC of engineering category if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can talk him/her. Assistant director told the name of Professor Dr. Md. Saidur Rahman and directed to the office of the UGC member. Under permission, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain met with Professor Dr. Md. Saidur Rahman, an UGC member, under the direction of PS to chairman. On 4 February 2025, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got a short time to introduce and discuss himself to UGC member. Possibly, he was busy. UGC member told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “you may talk with the director office, they will guide you.”

In the website of the university grants commission UGC, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t get English spelling of the name of director and chairman, UGC. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t get the full name of the chairman. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was also searching and searching in google. What is the necessity to keep Bengali website of UGC? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain do not know. UGC have/should have a good

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connection with the professor community of Bangladesh government. UGC may have a lacking to do practice/advertise of UGC affiliated professors. How can Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain get a good quality professor and/or ethical professor in Bangladesh? What should be the way and where is the public service of UGC? UGC is a place of PhD and research funding. UGC is a central administration of Bangladeshi universities. Personal secretary of UGC chairman should more understand about

What is UGC?

What is PhD?

What is the relevant function of an office of UGC chairman?

What is university in Bangladesh?

What is college in Bangladesh?

Please we need to understand firstly, we need to teach the university student accordingly. In Bangladesh, every college is giving bachelor degree through the university affiliation. So, every university student is getting service from UGC. So, every college is contributing as active university on behalf of vice chancellor on behalf of Bangladesh government. Bangladesh has huge numbers of university by name which are affiliated by UGC. There is huge deviation between the affiliation and monitoring. Possibly, affiliation or university grant is the key responsibility of the UGC. But UGC can not keep continue the quality of university. Every university should have research degree and research facilities without which Bangladesh should not increase the number of universities rather than colleges. Bangladesh should not introduce the name of university. Bangladesh should have a central university who should serve for the college and universities who have lack of research infrastructure. By the national and global act, every PhD category researcher should have legal permission to get support from other universities who have research infrastructures. Every university is a national wealth, no university is a private wealth of nobody. UGC should notify and clarify the acts and facts to the chairman of the private universities. Whatever, it is private ordinance and/or public regulation and/or college ordinance. Every private university or public university should be collaborated with the national or international category universities who are practicing more impact in higher education. A collaboration should be the requirement of quality score/affiliation score of a university.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent below e-mail to UGC chairman and director of Bangladesh government but the e-mail was bounced back immediately. So, what is the necessity to keep official e-mail address in the UGC website? (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Who is paying and monitoring for UGC website. Government money is also money. Government money should

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Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

not be the printed paper. The government money is the sacrificed money/beneficiary money of the Bangladeshi citizen.

Remarkable outcomes of applied law research at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Page | 9

Anowar Hossain

To: reza.hoseinnezhad@rmit.edu · Sun, Jun 8 at 7:39 PM

Message Body

Dear Sir/Madam,

I have attached two remarkable outcomes of applied law research at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia, Page 163-170.

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>

1. Legal approach of 'PhD compensation award of Australian government' of 8390000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD)

2. Legal approach of death penalty of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

To: me · Sun, Jun 8 at 7:30 PM

Visit site

1 Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

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<pschairman@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (pschairman@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

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Page | 10

To: me · Sun, Jun 8 at 7:30 PM

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2 Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>:

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MAILER-DAEMON@yahoo.com

To: me · Sun, Jun 8 at 7:30 PM

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3 Message Body

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<chairman@ugc.gov.bd>:

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4 Message Body

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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

<secretary@ugc.gov.bd>:

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1 Introduction

PhD by relation, PhD by motivation, PhD by certificate, PhD by marksheet, PhD by money, PhD by sex, PhD by practice, PhD by research, PhD by thesis, PhD by publication, PhD by invention should be well written in the PhD certificate (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024x). A PhD experience and PhD certificate should not be a common format of any university. A Postdoc experience and Postdoc certificate should not be a common format of any university. Invention and contribution of knowledge are the key requirement of PhD and Postdoc. There is scope of modification and development of national and global PhD and Postdoc philosophy. Professor Dr. Mubarak Hossain, Bangladeshi Scientist told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain on 4 February 2024, “after having successful milestone/three milestone, PhD student didn’t get PhD; so, one PhD student bulleted to his PhD supervisor in Australia when I did PhD in Australia.” Professor Dr. Mubarak Hossain, Bangladeshi Scientist told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain on 4 February 2024, “your supervisor is your second God.” It seems that everyone respects the professor by the blind philosophy and blind understanding. So, every professor should be careful and careful, ethical and ethical to supervise PhD and teaching the students. A scientist will create thousands of new ideas. Every tone of a scientist is an innovation. The whole world is enjoying the fruit of the scientists. If we can not utilize the scientist, if we can not right designate the scientist, we can not accelerate the national growth. Product development and marketing are not only a duty of a scientist. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain saw non-woven bag of Professor Dr. Mubarak Hossain, a product of technical textiles. Nobody can create a scientist. Scientist is self-made by chance. Scientist is self-motivated by chance. No government can reimburse to scientist. Government may motivate to scientist. God is an unseen government; professor is a seen government. God is by believe, professor is by practical. American government supposed to prefer penalty unit in terms of California bush fire if the God is a seen government. In general, high temperature versus warm air flowing are the reason of sourcing and extending the bush fire. In Australia, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain felt warm air in the summer season, it is very uncommon in Bangladesh. If naughty peoples smoke cigarette and make artificial fire, this is also the simple reason of artificial bush fire of any country. Although, smoking cigarette is a harmful fashion. It should be high punishable in public places all over the world. Professor Dr. Engr. Md.

Anowar Hossain practically saw a bush fire in Bangladesh in his local area whatever created by the naughty peoples who were smoking and enjoying cigarette. Sometimes, naughty peoples enjoy and enjoy the bush fire. So, every country should take care their forest in summer season.

2 Methodology of the letter of proceeding

Page | 12

- ✓ A life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT university is narrated to extend the action and support of Australian government, Bangladesh government, and united nations (UN) (2021-2025) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).
- ✓ Private university of Bangladesh government is mostly cited and investigated for City University of Bangladesh government. There are also highlighting the general remarks about Bangladeshi private universities (2006-2025). The data collection of this higher education and research was started since 2005-2006 at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and private/public universities in Bangladesh, India, and Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)(Hossain, 2023c).
- ✓ As Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is writing this letter to convince the central committee of Bangladesh government and Australian government where is limitation of law implementation of private university/City University of Bangladesh and RMIT University of Australia. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not be liable for any limitation of any country for any professional and academic growth and professional growth due to the moment of fund crisis, assessment of this letter, legal support, and assessment of law implementation department.
- ✓ A study of higher education, PhD education, compensation in academia, compensation in profession, and global issue remarked for the development of higher education and research in India, Australia and Bangladesh.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Human philosophy of force, respect, and honour in academia and public administration

An MTech (Master of Technology) in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) student in University of Calcutta was so much angry with a professor in the laboratory exam hall. The student started to beat a professor, the neck side of a professor by hand by hand. Still the professor tried to control the student. Still the student got the MTech degree. Now the student is teaching at the same department. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain practiced lifelong in opposite direction. If professor try to kill him, try to conspire him at RMIT University, still Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain say/said, “your honour, your honour, respected professor, respected professor.” Still the professor is not happy, so the professor is not a professor. Blind respect is also

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a symptom of criminal offence when we are adult. People should not write respected professor when professor is a self-word of respect. Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain officially wrote and added 'respected' before the word of professor at RMIT university who tried and conspired to kill Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. People should not write honorable president, honourable chancellor, honourable vice chancellor, honourable chairman, his excellency prime minister, his excellency high commissioner, etc. The words of professor, president, chancellor, prime minister, and vice chancellor are the symbol of honour and honour. Practically, we do not mix milk with milk, honey with honey to make a recipe. Sometimes, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw the mother who beat her son or daughter who beat her son or daughter because of simple mistake or zero mistake when the mother is adult. If a mother can not self-control, this is the mistake of mother, this is a brain disease symptom of mother and/or crime of mother. Mother still loughs or sacrifices if non-adult child slap or beat to mother.

3.2 Self-funded Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, BSc, MTech, PhD¹ Tech (M. A. Hossain, 2023ca, 2023cb)

University grants commission (UGC) should have a public service to serve PhD researcher in general. UGC should have public consultancy support for the PhD researchers who are also serving in national and international platform. A PhD consultant post may be created by the UGC or the UGC member should be responsible for this official service. Every university may have a post of PhD consultant for a public service or every professor should be judicially responsible for this public service. Where should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain go if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have PhD issue if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain need consultancy support? Every PhD researcher should continue preliminary plan or discussion to solve the critical issue who should take this liability who should bear this cost if PhD or publication are the prerequisite of university promotion of a country? (M. A. Hossain, 2023ah)(Hossain, 2023b) Therefore Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-funded for PhD¹ in Textile Technology before going to Australian PhD school. Private university is afraid and afraid about PhD funding. Because/somehow, the profit of a private university is the profit of the chairman of the trustee board. So, they should not write private university, they should write only 'private'. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is confusing about the UGC liability and creditability to run the private universities in Bangladesh. Private university students are self-funding to be a graduate of the university. Similarly, private university teachers should self-fund/contribute to be a professor of the same university. This is also a situation of confusing and harassing for the professional growth. So, what is the research funding philosophy of a private university in Bangladesh? So, what is the philosophy of a private university? What should be the solution? Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a self-funded professor and self-

funded graduate, post graduate, and PhD¹ in Textile Technology (2006-2025) (A. Hossain, 2020; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; Hossain, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2023ca, 2023cb; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019).

3.3 Scholarship funded PhD² thesis and peer reviewed PhD² thesis to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)

Page | 14

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to recommend to make an anonymous committee (national and/or international) for the quality guidance/support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist under the quality funding of UGC, government of Bangladesh and/or education department of Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is officially representing and submitting his invention to the chairman of UGC, Bangladesh and education department of Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also attaching a peer review history (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024f) of his PhD² thesis (M. A. Hossain, 2023g) and/or Nobel prize¹ thesis (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g) to store color printed copy in the PhD Museum of UGC of Bangladesh government and/or general museum of Bangladesh government. A separate funding is also necessary for the process. A first version of PhD² thesis submitted to RMIT University and peer reviewed by RMIT University from 5 February 2020 to 4 February 2021 (M. A. Hossain, 2023al). A second version of PhD² thesis submitted to RMIT University and peer reviewed by RMIT University from 5 February 2021 to 4 February 2022 (M. A. Hossain, 2023ak, 2023bc). A third version of PhD² thesis and/or Nobel prize thesis was externally peer reviewed by the publication process as prerequisite of RMIT University since 5 February 2022 to still now (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g). A third version of PhD² thesis was externally submitted in publication process of PhD² thesis and peer reviewed under the full-time PhD² service under the life-threatening conspiracy, and PhD² conspiracy of Australian PhD school (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023ak, 2023bc; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024f)

3.4 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) approached PhD compensation award of Australian government

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a Bangladeshi and Australian PhD victim (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024e). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked his life time safety to Australian government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked his safety in Bangladesh and Australia to the Australian government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a long-term PhD sufferer. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to attach the brief history of his PhD harassment in terms of scholarly convincing. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain claimed a 'PhD compensation award' of 230,72,50,000AUD of Australian government. PhD harassment is also the invention of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for the peace of global PhD schooling for global quality of higher education and quality safety of professor and researcher community (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

3.5 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) asked/asking compensation support/administrative support to Australian high commissioner in Bangladesh, Bangladeshi high commissioner in Australia, chief advisor, president, and foreign secretary of Bangladesh (Hossain, 2024c)

On 4 February 2025, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain went to the Dhaka office of Australian high commissioner, chancellor, chief advisor, and foreign secretary of Bangladesh government. On 4 February 2025 at 11:10-11:20 am, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain physically visited the office of Australian high commission in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain had a discussion with the front desk officials. Firstly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain approached himself as Australian PhD student and Australian student VISA. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain approached and asked about the condition of his submitted letters to Australian high commissioner since 2022-2025 (M. A. Hossain, 2023b; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024j). On 4 February 2025, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain also submitted a summary of his submitted letters to the office high commissioner. Front desk didn't issue him any receipt evidence of Dr. Anwar's letters on 4 February 2025. Front desk person told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, "I will give you back the letter if you ask any receipt evidence of the letter." Front desk noted the name and mobile numbers of Dr. Anwar. Front desk asked and heard the summery of the letters and/or reasons of the meeting at high commissioner office. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain also asked to front desk if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain can meet or talk with the high commissioner. Later front desk official told to Dr. Anwar, "we only serve Australian citizen holders in the office of Australian high commission, we will submit the letter to the high commissioner." Possibly, G and S security team was serving and controlling the whole front desk of Australian high commission. On 4 February 2025, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain also visited the front desk of president office and chief advisor office in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2024c). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain asked the conditions of letters, but the front desk had no information about the posted letters (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024k). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain submitted the whole summery of letters in 2024. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain also requested an appointment as public or Bangladeshi citizen. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain got a receiving seal and signature on behalf of the front desk of chief advisor and president of Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023b; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024j, 2024k)(Hossain, 2024c).

3.6 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) asking compensation and collaboration support to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and President, RMIT University

Figure 1, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent around 100 letters to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and President, RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023bc). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent letters to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron and Professor Alice Payne. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent cc letters to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and Professor Alice Payne, Dean, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University. Every professional person and/or relevant officials are responsible for a cc letter. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to talk with Professor Dr. Alec Cameron on 17 February 2025. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was failing to communicate with him and his stuffs with the following telephone numbers in Australian office hours, figure 1 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k). The website was active on 17 February 2025, but the telephone numbers were not active on 17 February 2025. Later, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also telephoned to +61 3 9925 2000 through the support of telephone operator of RMIT University who asked the reason of telephone calling who separately forwarded the telephone call to vice chancellor and dean. Both Professor Dr. Alec Cameron and Professor Alice Payne were unable to receive the telephone call in Australian office hours. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-funded telephoned to vice chancellor and Professor Alice Payne. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is afraid if vice chancellor and his office stuffs are getting salary, Dean is getting salary or administrative allowance of Australian government. Who should take care the RMIT University if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is writing and practicing the affiliation of RMIT University if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is lifelong take caring and investing for the brand value of RMIT University? Who should take care the student/researcher of RMIT University? Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is taking the lifelong liability of this brand of RMIT University. Present vice chancellor is not a former graduate of RMIT University. So, possibly he is not establishing and increasing the brand value of RMIT University. If Professor Dr. Alec Cameron and Professor Alice Payne are not happy to extend their ethical service to ensure the ethical voice of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in terms of life-threatening conspiracy; everyone should have penalty/compensation award of 10, 000 Australian penalty unit under the support of Australian education act, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023c). Professor Dr. Alec Cameron and Professor Alice Payne should pay the compensation award to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is afraid to judge a vice chancellor, but protesting and informing about life threatening issues are the Australian quality of research framework whatever officially taught to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australian PhD school. Ethical services are the routine responsibility of any vice chancellor of any university of any country. Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar

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 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTEch, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design PLC, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite PLC, Radix PLC, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: S12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar, Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain got two response letters of Australian prime minister, but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get any response letter of vice chancellor, RMIT University. If vice chancellor is failing to continue his routine duty, if he is failing to ensure the rights of researcher, he should get a punishment. In terms of longer assessment period, the value of compensation award of RMIT University should increase parallelly and parallelly should be paid to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. We can not just forward to court whatever expensive process for an international PhD researcher in Australia. If judicial court is better than university court, university court/professor court should be banned. University court/professor court should be more ethical than the judicial court if university is the mother of the judicial court. Every university is also a court of professor community. Every peer review is also a PhD court. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also submitting this letter to the court of UGC, Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted self-life-threatening conspiracy to the court of vice chancellor, RMIT University. Every court is the symbol of human right and ethical beauty. In 2021-2022, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked and requested the support of university court and/or university committee. Then, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain requested to high court of Australia. Possibly, high court need to appoint professor category lawyer to solve the PhD issue versus life threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not getting student visa without repeated offer letter of vice chancellor of RMIT University. This is not a matter of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, this is an issue of professor community, this is an issue of PhD community, this is an issue of Australian government, this is an issue of international community, this is an issue of ethical community, this is the issue of vice chancellor, RMIT University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain officially sent a complain letter of self-life-threatening to vice chancellor in 2021-2022. But the office of vice chancellor was performing as non-active representative on behalf of RMIT University, Australia on behalf of Australian government. Professor Dr. Alec Cameron is internationally advertising the post of vice chancellor but he is self-neglecting to extend his self-service as a vice chancellor at RMIT University. Who should take the liability, officiality, and professionalism of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron if he is the registered vice chancellor of RMIT University if he is the registered ambassador of RMIT University if he is the chief executive officer of quality assurance of RMIT University? The official recommendation and crime analysis are very important to assess official life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. Professor Dr. Alec Cameron can go to Birla Institute of Technology, India (2023-2024), but he can not come to Bangladesh to solve the international issue to solve the long-term international issue. UGC may discuss the scope of 'education friendship between Bangladesh and Australia', 'education friendship between India and Bangladesh', 'education friendship among Australia, Bangladesh

and India'. Let's practice higher education weapon for the peace of mankind. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain believe that Bangladesh government is also trying, maintaining, funding, and structuring strong platform of higher education and excellency in education. Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is the lifelong ambassador of friendship in higher education and research. Vice chancellor, RMIT university should come to Bangladesh to announce the 'education friendship between Bangladesh and Australia'. Bangladeshi universities and RMIT University may sign student exchange program under the satisfied terms and conditions of the both countries. Both universities can also continue marriage program to enhance a biological relation between Bangladesh and Australia.

<p>Professor Alec Cameron is the Vice-Chancellor and President of RMIT.</p> <p>Contacting the Vice-Chancellor</p> <p>Postal address GPO Box 2476 Melbourne VIC 3001 Australia Email: vc@rmit.edu.au</p> <p>Brooke Griffin Chief of Staff Tel: +61 3 9925 9710 Email: brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au</p> <p>Margie Wright Senior Executive Coordinator Tel: +613 9925 1999 Email: ea_vc@rmit.edu.au</p> <p>Jason Ngam Senior Principal Advisor Tel: +613 9925 5761 Email: jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au</p> <p>Nicole Hendrie Executive Assistant to Chief of Staff Tel: +613 9925 1999 Email: nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au</p>	<p>PROFESSOR Alice Payne</p> <p>ID 0000-0002-1570-6378</p> <p>Dean, School of Fashion & Textiles Design and Social Context</p> <p>alice.payne@rmit.edu.au</p> <p>Brunswick, Australia</p>	
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Figure 1. non-active telephone numbers of Professor Dr. Alice Payne, Dean, School of Fashion and Textiles; and Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and President, RMIT University, Australia in Australian office hours on 17 February 2025, cited in website on 17 February 2025. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respect the post of vice chancellor and dean. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not respect the non-active post of vice chancellor and dean since 2021-2022 to satisfy the right duty of international life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.

RMIT has no Bachelor degree in Textile Engineering, if RMIT University and City University and/or other university can do collaboration. RMIT University may sign the student transfer with Bangladeshi universities if both universities agree to proceed jointly if both universities happy to proceed international collaboration of BSc/MSc engineering degree and higher degree by research. But Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye should not continue with education service if he is being continued his hidden business of killing conspiracy and illegal sex issue through the hidden support of

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 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design PLC, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite PLC, Radix PLC, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
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education business of Australian education department. He should not involve with any education service of Bangladesh, India, and Australia if he is doing killing conspiracy to PhD candidate in Australian PhD school if he is the education enemy of Bangladesh, India, and Australia rather than education service. These are the symptom of international crime against the global education policy against the global surviving policy against the international relationship policy against the international believe, friendship, and happiness. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to claim the death penalty of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye under the assessment support of high court of Australia, support of Australian education act, and the support of international education act if he is doing crime in Bangladesh and Australia. There is still lack of international education act. UN should monitor the international education act for the global excellency of higher education and research. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also notifying this letter to the office of Professor V. Ramgopal Rao, Vice Chancellor, Birla Institute of Technology, India and Chairman, UGC of India. Possibly, Australian education minister is not a minister of RMIT University. Possibly, dean of school of fashion and textiles is not a dean of RMIT University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also sent around 100 letters and/or cc e-mail to education minister and education department of Australia, and dean of School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University. They had no answer or action to investigate the conspiracy of life threatening in Australian PhD school. But the vice chancellor of RMIT University is busy to work with Birla Institute of Technology, India. As referred to Bangladeshi newspaper in Bangladesh, Australian government also offered education business to Bangladesh government in 2022-2023. Ms. Penny Wong, Foreign Minister and/or Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade, The Commonwealth of Australia also came to Bangladesh in 2022-2023. If RMIT University is doing life threatening conspiracy, PhD conspiracy, family conspiracy, and safety conspiracy; the education service of RMIT university should be expelled in Australia and India under the international education act and/or support of the UN. Vice chancellor, RMIT University should guide to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to solve the international issue of life-threatening conspiracy. Vice chancellor should not be afraid to continue his ethical service at RMIT University. Australian government awarding and respecting to vice chancellor through the prestigious post of vice chancellor. If Professor Dr. Alec Cameron is a vice chancellor if vice chancellor is a respected post in the global platform if he is the respected person for the post, he should be liable to eliminate and investigate life-threatening conspiracy in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school.

3.7 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) organized collaboration meeting between BGMEA University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh and University of Calcutta, India

In December 2019, in a meeting in Bangladesh, Professor Dr. Ayub Nabi Khan, BGMEA University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh offered and proposed to Professor Dr. AK Samanta, University of Calcutta, India if BGMEA can collaborate with University of Calcutta. Collaboration generates and ensures quality learning, cultural understanding, cultural exchange, global quality of higher education, brand sharing, and professional excellency. Although the self-studying in foreign countries is also an official collaboration of a country to country by which way self-student contributes for the nation for the global excellency. Every collaboration act may be standardized in international platform of higher education act and research act. Every university degree may have an addition of foreign education tour and training to enhance international and educational excellency. Therefore, locally and internationally; every university may be connected with different universities to enhance the quality learning, quality branding, and quality standing.

Page | 20

3.8 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) asked legal support at door to door in Bangladesh

On 4 February 2025 to 5 February 2025, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was searching an international category lawyer, expert lawyer to know the process and cost of international court processing. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited the office of Dr. Kamal Hossen, Bangladeshi lawyer for inquiry and information. Firstly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain met with the office representative. Office receptionist didn't tell to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain anything about the fees who sequentially arranged the appointment with personal secretary of secretary and secretary of the lawyer office. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain wanted to know the cost summery for an international court. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked to personal secretary of secretary, "I need a letter of cost summery for filing a case in international court." Later, the secretary of Dr. Kamal Hossen asked and interviewed Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, about Dr. Anowar's family, Dr. Anowar's baby, Dr. Anowar's place of residence, and Dr. Anowar's age. Secretary told to Dr. Anowar to build a family. Secretary asked to Dr. Anowar, "how did you come to this office? When will you take baby or when will you build family?" Secretary of lawyer's office told to Dr. Anowar, "I was a medical student, I can understand man." Secretary of lawyer's office told to Dr. Anowar, "you didn't earn money in your whole life; we charge 500USD per hour for international case; possibly you can not pay money; so, you are wasting our time." Secretary of lawyer's office told to Dr. Anowar, "we normally see the company matters, we don't deal with the international matters, Dr. Kamal Hossen is not coming to office, he is sick. You may search another law firm, nearest law firm, there is also another law firm." Secretary of lawyer's office told to Dr. Anowar, "you may start earning money." (M. A. Hossain, 2023au; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023ch, 2023ci) Later secretary

<p>Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020) Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025) Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg) University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assisist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design PLC, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite PLC, Radix PLC, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar, Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	
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told to Dr. Anowar, “we also charge 5000USD for international case, pay 5000USD.” So, the income is good of a lawyer if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can be the casual consultant of critical legal case in national and international platform. So, the law firm may forward international case to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. As additional duty of RMIT University, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also practiced Australian Barrister (Dr.) since 6 July 2022. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also practicing Australian Barrister as additional duty of RMIT University on behalf of RMIT University. The website of this law firm had also mentioned legal aid service on 4-5 February 2025. If the law firm has no legal aid service, they should not advertise in the website. Every lawyer or legal consultant may hang a chart of consultancy fees. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't see the lawyer fees or chart anywhere in Bangladesh any law firm or law chamber in Bangladesh/India. How can a client understand a legal fees of a legal consultant? Therefore, a victim is begging and begging door to door, man to man, lawyer to lawyer, office to office, high court to high court, scientist to scientist, professor to professor, vice chancellor to vice chancellor, president to president, bar association to bar association, country to country, and UGC to UGC. Possibly, Bangladesh and Australia have no international legal aid service. Every country should have international legal aid service for the support of international category victim. So, what is the situation of human right to international victim if Bangladesh government and/or UGC can recommend to UN to approve national and international legal aid service to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; if foreign ministry of Bangladesh government can extend their international service to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; if foreign ministry of Australian government can extend their international service to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; if the vice chancellor of RMIT University can extend their international service to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; if the education ministry of Australian government can extend their international service to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Hossain, 2025b)? (M. A. Hossain, 2023bu).

3.9 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) asked/asking legal support and administrative support to Bangladesh government

If eligible, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to approach the following key points for the consideration of UGC, chancellor, chief advisor, education minister/ministry of Bangladesh government, and education minister/ministry of Bangladesh government under the assessment support of UGC chairman and members and relevant authorities.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek a protest letter to Australian government and/or Australian high commissioner against the life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school and lifelong safety to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh and Australia. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek an official protest letter on behalf of whole vice chancellors in Bangladesh on behalf of all Bangladeshi universities, on behalf of whole vice chancellors in Australia on behalf of all Australian universities, and international universities.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek a letter to Bangladesh government/chief advisor/prime minister/president to extend international legal aid service against the life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school and lifelong safety to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh and Australia.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek a letter to Australian government/prime minister to extend international legal aid service against the life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school and lifelong safety to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh and Australia.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek a letter to UN to extend international legal aid service against the life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school and permanent safety to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh and Australia.
- ✓ Every university lecturer should get a minimum fund to be a professor without which research and publication should not be a prerequisite for the promotion of a university professor (Hossain, 2023b). A student can not self-fund life-time. Bangladesh government may start professor training/promotion institute by which way lecturer may get a quality guidance to be a quality professor in public and private universities. Who should start? What is the action and support of UGC to make a professor/ quality professor in private universities? What is the action and support of education ministry? What is the relevant function of education ministry? Should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invest lifelong in private university? Should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invest lifelong to Bangladesh government? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a person; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not an organization.
- ✓ UGC should grant university who have a plan to certify research degree, research service, knowledge creation, fully English medium education, and a quality education. We grant award to people for personal excellency and university gets value in terms of awardee or personal excellency. Similarly, university may also get award. But university is a group name to continue the professional service and support in national and international platform.

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✓ Nationally and internationally, every PhD committee member and/or promotion committee member should get a quality allowance to certify the PhD degree by research to certify PhD degree by mark sheet to certify the PhD degree by routine teaching and learning if the PhD is a matter of certified degree if the PhD is not a matter of relationship if the PhD is not a matter of joking in nationally and internationally. It is also possible to certify a PhD degree to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain by submitting, accepting, and assessing this case letter. Now Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can write or propose a PhD thesis every day when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain take morning tea but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not do self-PhD registration every day, the PhD registration should be one time and one time. Every PhD degree should have a marks sheet if it is being claimed as an academic degree. Without which PhD and Postdoc are professional practice under the academic supervision and professional guidance. Every university mark sheet may have a name of supervisor or instructor from bachelor to PhD degree/Postdoc degree. PhD without marks sheet should be banned in national and international platform if PhD is an academic degree rather than professional practice. Nobody can assess a five years duration PhD by a piece of certified paper of a vice chancellor. Logically and practically, PhD by research should be a professional degree, professional learning, professional contribution, and professional rank. If a degree has no marks sheet, it should be a professional degree/professional practice whatever being trended now. Although PhD by research is being practiced under the academic platform and academic supervision. How many PhD thesis should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submit? How many PhD registration should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain do? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got certified Indian MTech degree. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get value in the government assessment of Bangladesh due to having affiliation of a private university/City University in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got certified Bangladeshi BSc (Bachelor of Science) in Textile Engineering degree. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get value in government assessment of Bangladesh. Corruption is everywhere, corruption in academia, corruption in the appointment of the Bangladesh government. An appointment policy should not be a financial business of a committee. It seems that nobody is guardian of the country and/or scholarly organizations. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is showing and advertising his RMIT PhD since 2019-2020 to still now (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024m). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have also attached in this letter accordingly. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was also

practicing PhD research since 2015-2016(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz) after completion his MTech/MPhil degree in 2015 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

- ✓ Every university correspondence, teaching, and learning should be international, should be 100% English. It should be legally approved in Bangladesh.
- ✓ A separate chancellor post may be created to lead the university and/or higher education on behalf of Bangladesh government. An emeritus professor or an experienced holder scientist may also be connected with a university as a chief leader or a chancellor who should visit the laboratory who should visit the professor who should guide the professor who should talk with the university who should talk with the lecturer who should add a value to the university to the central government to the ministry of education. Every private university of Bangladesh may have a chancellor, governed by funded by UGC and ministry of education.
- ✓ Every profession may take an approval of dress code from office assistant to chief executive officer to enhance professional motivation and professional excellency. Every government employee may have a standard dress code with the symbol of ethical beauty. Minister, chief minister and president may have a special dress code for their professional duty and excellency. If we see British Indian administration, they had a dress code with the technological design and fashionable motivation. If we see British Indian vice chancellor of university, they had a dress code with the technological design and fashionable motivation. But presently, Bangladesh and India have no administrative dress code. A dress code is an administrative motivation and administrative symbol. A dress code is a symbol of administrative honour, administrative motivation, good feeling, and good commanding. Every good feeling, every good looking are the motivation for a quality administration. So, we are gradually declining the administrative motivation rather than improving the administrative fashion and design when we are technologically improving the fashion design (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). As a professional textile engineer, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to recommend a common dress code of university student, university professor, vice chancellor, and chancellor of Bangladesh government and/or international governments by putting a monogram of 'ethical beauty' who are the representative of global ethics who are the ambassador of global ethics. Although university have a dress code of convocation, but the dress code of black gown and cap are not being practiced for a daily schooling. Bangladesh Textile University may propose the exact design of the dress code on behalf of Bangladesh government in Bangladesh. RMIT University may propose the exact design of the dress code on behalf of Australian government in Australia. Professor Dr. Lijing Wang and his research team at RMIT University may propose a dress code to Australian government. Relevant PhD or research

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funding may be approved and signed by the relevant authority of Bangladesh government and Australian government (M. A. Hossain, 2023as)(Hossain, 2023c).

- ✓ One to one PhD supervision between male and female appears to the joint function like hero and heroine in movie, but hero and heroine are not a married couple, but hero and heroine are professional. Government may practice of woman university if government needs specialized lady experts or PhD holder experts in different fields of administration. PhD by hidden sex should not be allowed. If PhD by sex is allowed, it should have a permitted rule of the UGC act or education act of the country, it can be officially assessed and commented by the national and international professor community and relevant experts if it is applicable if it is natural if it is biological if it is professional if it is research friendly if it is Australia friendly. If one to one PhD supervision is valid, if one to one scientist supervision is valid, if one to one opposite gender supervision is valid in research organization for a long-term duration, one to one sex may be valid under the assessment of approved act or scientist act of professor community (M. A. Hossain, 2023as, 2023bc). Practically, the job functions, employing, and placement of male and female should be well separated to minimize sex crime and sex hassle everywhere. Every government should monitor the biological and natural facts for the placement of male and female in the professional offices and professional ethics. Moreover, marriage facilities of university students and teachers should be supported and increased under the marriage program and education act to minimize sex crime in university and research centre.
- ✓ In general, university students are taking leading power all over the world. If the ethical standard is less than 50%, university degree may be terminated in the professional journey under the central committee of UGC and/or a government and/or a university. A certified university degree should be partial; a certified university degree should not be permanent. Such way, every university may contribute or supervise or practice to establish zero crime all over the world.
- ✓ We will need to initiate zero cost theory of a government to minimize currency inflation all over the world. We need to initiate zero cost theory of defence when the defence of every country is expensive and expensive. We will need to initiate zero cost theory of teaching, learning, and higher education. Every university student may serve as defence soldier when necessary for the country under the alarming situation of a country under the crisis situation of a country in terms of joint act of education ministry and defence ministry of the country. Nobody should/can cease any flag/peace of any country without legal reason. For example: India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh are 'three brother countries' who were gradually separated from the British India. So, Bangladesh should get equal land

property. Bangladesh is a comparatively small country than Pakistan and India. If Bangladesh didn't get equal land property, Bangladesh should get ethical support of Pakistan and India to extend the national and global service and survive. Historically, Bangladesh invested blood and blood in 1971. Every country should deny the bloody policy. There is also another policy. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to make friendship with Indian researcher, Pakistani researcher, and Pakistani medical practitioner in Australia. By nature, we give value of our brothership, sistership, friendship, and neighbourship. We try to practice good relationship. No government should continue/harm/conspire the relationship injury. These are the symptom of international crime. Three-to-six-month duration defence training should continue for the university students. Every university student may serve as defence service during extreme moment of the country. Every university student may have a common dress code of defence. Therefore, government can also minimize the defence cost when government are also investing for the university students. If necessary, government can make new university campuses behind the border area and/or village area. Capital city is not a good place of education centre. We can also start the university of defence technology and/or the department of defence technology. Every government should motivate to follow and invest for protection, negotiation, and relationship technique instead of fire arms technique. Every country tries to display their fire arms. Every fire arm is expensive and highly destructive, long terms destructive against the peace of human being against the peace of normal surviving in the planet. Nobody likes to face fire arms and fire arms. Nobody can reimburse the victim of the fire arms. The research of fire arms and atomic weapon and implementation rules may be scrutinized by the relevant government and UN. Nobody should continue destructive research of atomic energy and fire arms rather than peaceful research rather than peaceful surviving. People can not eat food, people can not invest for education and medical, people need to purchase fire arms by force, people need to invest for fire arms by force. These are confusing situation and confusing scenery of global community. So, may Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain approach zero crime for the global community through the education department of Bangladesh government and Australian government through the global education policy.

- ✓ Bangladesh government, Australian government, Indian government should jointly assess if the Australian criminal has any connection with the local politicians or criminals in Australia, Bangladesh and/or Indian community. Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a director, he is not a paid professor, he is not a paid consultant of criminal investigation department of any country (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023ch, 2023ci).
- ✓ Every UGC chairman and member may serve as the equivalent power of parliament member (non-democratic) of Bangladesh government. This is also necessary to solve the

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critical problem to assess the governmental decision to assess the international relation in the political leadership to survive in crisis moment of the country.

- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain needs a designation in foreign ministry if foreign ministry of Bangladesh government can not perform the job of Australia dealing about the life-threatening conspiracy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain needs a designation to continue the legal service and action such as director, foreign affairs (Australia).
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek an investigation of UGC about life threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. UGC may generate a report about life threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek a research fund (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek safety support through the Bangladesh government, Australian government, interpol, and UN funding.
- ✓ Every government can make a central museum of death penalty report for the law students, relevant researcher, crime reporters, and general peoples. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to submit a data bank for a crime of a death penalty (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).
- ✓ Melbourne is a very expensive city. It is better to be graduate in self-country rather than wasting time with casual job who are aiming to pursue self-funding higher education in Australia who can not manage Australian schooling and living costs. Accordingly, Bangladesh and Australia should have a proper counselling centre in college/university/ministry/embassy. Nobody should misguide the students. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw Bangladeshi female student of graduate level who was doing casual job in meat shop in Melbourne. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw Bangladeshi and Nepali male students of graduate level who were doing casual job in vegetable shop, fruit shop, and cleaning job in Melbourne. So, what will be the full-time education experience in Australia?
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek recommendation to carry international category portable and light weight (proportionally to hand weight) personal arms, and UGC approved arms if eligible. Parallely, there is also a matter of safety of the personal weapon.
- ✓ If nobody ceases single dollar of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in his profession in Bangladesh and Australia, he supposed to survive his whole life in Bangladesh without doing any routine job, but his pocket is almost empty now, but he needs to go to national court/Australian court/international court for his earned money and/or achieved money.

Bangladesh and Australia should support jointly to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every God father should get punishment, although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respect them second God.

- ✓ Australia and/or Bangladesh may recommend a movie in the name of ‘PhD tragedy in Australia’ in the name of ‘higher education friendship between Bangladesh and Australia’. The movie should be/may be jointly funded by Australia and Bangladesh. At first day in a PhD school, every PhD student may watch the movie in national and international PhD school to satisfy self-safety in a PhD school (Hossain, 2023d).
- ✓ Education and research wing of UN should not neglect the safety of a professor or scientist. Education wing of UN, education ministry of Australia, education ministry of Bangladesh, foreign ministry of Australia, foreign ministry of Bangladesh should forcefully recommend to confirm the safety and right research placement to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to any reputed university and/or research organization of Australia, United Kingdom, United States of America, and UN.
- ✓ Education and research wing of UN, education ministry of Australia, education ministry of Bangladesh, foreign ministry of Australia, foreign ministry of Bangladesh should forcefully recommend to assess and approve the ‘PhD compensation award’ of Australian government of 230,72,50,000AUD to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under the assessment support of high court of Australia and/or international court.
- ✓ Education and research wing of UN, education ministry of Australia, education ministry of Bangladesh, foreign ministry of Australia, foreign ministry of Bangladesh, UGC of Bangladesh, UGC of India, government of United States of America, government of China, government of Russia, government of United Kingdom may assess the feasibility of research fund, feasibility of post-doctoral fund to enhance the ‘international education act’ in terms of legal stipend or legal support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist.
- ✓ Safety in universities should be highly improved, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw security peoples in front of class room at City University in 2006-2010 at Banani campus, Dhaka. He saw gun man in front of main gate, Panthapath campus, City University, Bangladesh in 2017-2019. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw security peoples in front of permanent campus, City University, Bangladesh. Possibly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t see any gun man at University of Calcutta, India (2013-2015); Bangladesh agricultural university, Bangladesh (2023); and RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t see any gun man in front of pro vice chancellor office of University of Calcutta, India and vice chancellor office of Bangladesh agricultural university (2023). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw a gun man at vice chancellor office of University of Dhaka who had a non-

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professional dress code (2023). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw security peoples in front of vice chancellor and pro vice chancellor office of Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (2023). But, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw many gun mans and defence peoples at president and chief advisor office of Bangladesh government (2025).

3.10 Crime of Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman at Department of Textile Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh and harassed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) at RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023c)

Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman, Department of Textile Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh tried, forced, and harassed to put name in the PhD² publication (M. A. Hossain, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024m) of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University, tried to make professional harassment to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, tried to make verbal harassment to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, dishonored the decision of Australian government, tried to know health history of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australia and negatively commented, tried to know the history of surrounding peoples/known peoples of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australia, tried to make dress code harassment in Australia to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024y), tried to make performance harassment in Australia to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, showed seniority crime in Australia to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, showed scholarly crime for his self-promotion and professional growth at Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology. Possibly Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman planned to get promotion at Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology by the publication of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University, Australia. How is it possible? He forgot and forgot, but he tried and tried for his self-benefit. As per telephonic discussion and reference with Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman (2021), he had a connection with Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia. Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman also connected with Ms. Tanushree, Department of Textile Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh; and Dr. Faruk, Bangladesh Textile University, Bangladesh to communicate with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman like second God. So, Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman should have administrative punishment and penalty/compensation award of 10000 Australian penalty unit, the penalty unit should pay to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; and academic punishment of two promotion drop (2021-) at Department of Textile Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology

of Bangladesh government, UGC approved universities in Bangladesh, RMIT University of Australia, and international universities (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). It is also being mentioned the crimes and approached death penalty of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia due to having his criminal activities in Bangladesh and Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, and Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye like second God (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

3.11 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) asking/asked financial support through the law project of Bangladesh government and/or Australian government

Since 2022, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't hear any judicious support and speech from any community or organization, government offices, government leaders, university leaders, professor community, Australian political leaders, Bangladeshi political leaders in terms of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is unable to invest to continue research and study on behalf of any government. Hence, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like seek a quality placement support and/or to be a vice chancellor and research professor of a renowned public university or research institute under the safety of Bangladesh government if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have a valid citizen identity of Bangladesh government. By which way, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain may have a scope to serve ethically to survive ethically for the nation for the support of higher education for the global peace of mankind. By which way, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain may get a life-long compensation support, minimum compensation support for surviving whatever Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not recover personally for surviving as unit of human being. May Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also seek relevant action and support to get 'Australian PhD compensation award' of 230,72,50,000AUD. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking to Australian high court to pay 8390000 Australian penalty unit/PhD compensation award (230,72,50,000AUD) when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not claim to court due to self-financial crisis and administrative difficulties of Australian government. This is not the professional or personal duty of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to solve the administrative difficulties and/or limitations of Australian government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a paid professor or a paid consultant of Australian government to solve the administrative difficulties of RMIT University (M. A. Hossain, 2023a) (M. A. Hossain, 2023c) (M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b). Practically, Bangladesh government supports to bank by paying printed money by paying crore crore money. Bangladesh government support to industrialist by paying printed money. Similarly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to request for a reimbursement and

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 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
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surviving support of his lifetime investment in education if UGC is the right official leader of Bangladesh government (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq, 2023au; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not take life time liability of City University brand. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also seek a recommendation and compensation support through education ministry, vice chancellor and chancellor of City University, vice chancellor and chancellor of RMIT University, foreign ministry of different countries, president of different countries, chief advisor of different countries, UN, national legal aids, international legal aids for the relevant action and support.

Figure 2. PhD² tragedy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)

3.12 PhD² tragedy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) and asking support to Australia and Bangladesh

In general, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist faced financial harassment in his PhD² education under the following conditions of a PhD² tragedy, figure 2. If Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not getting legal aid support and/or free of cost legal support of Bangladesh government or Australian government or

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

UN or human rights communities; there is limitation of legal support, there is limitation of law implementation, there is limitation of government policy, there is limitation of ethical practice, there is limitation of UN, there is limitation to respect PhD community, there is limitation to respect researcher community, there is limitation to respect professor community, there is limitation to respect human right, there is limitation to respect the international higher education, there is limitation to respect Australian higher education, there is limitation to respect education friendship between Australia and Bangladesh. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is writing and writing for the global peace in PhD school and global security in PhD school.

- ✓ City University illegally stopped salary during study leave since February 2020 to pursue PhD² in Australia (Hossain, 2023e).
- ✓ RMIT University illegally stopped salary during study leave since 6 July 2022 (Hossain, 2023d).
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was unable to claim to Australian court due to financial crisis (Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023f; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2024a, 2024b).
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had self-funded BSc Engg, MTech, and PhD¹ in Textile Engineering to pursue PhD² in Textile Technology at RMIT University, Australia.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye continued his life-threatening conspiracy in PhD school.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye intentionally continued safety harassment in PhD school and possibly expanded to Bangladesh.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye applied his conspiracy technique in Bangladesh and Australia for his personal benefit and illegal gain.
- ✓ RMIT PhD school and/or Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye illegally involved with family; and Bangladeshi and Australian colleagues.
- ✓ Seriously collapsed family life due to financial crisis in PhD journey at RMIT University.
- ✓ Collapsed family relation due to illegal involvement of Australian PhD school.
- ✓ Parallely, family tried to cease land property (birthright) during PhD education.
- ✓ RMIT PhD school/Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye killed Dr. Anowar's family life/sex life through the illegal weapon of PhD school through the illegal connection in Bangladesh through the illegal power.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not take the support of Bangladesh defence force to pursue PhD at RMIT PhD school. RMIT should pay the whole office allowance during the moment of safety crisis and crisis of quality of life in PhD school.
- ✓ During Dr. Anowar's PhD education, RMIT university didn't take his fooding and living responsibility since 6 July 2022. These are the symptom of unethical demotivation to a PhD scientist.

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- ✓ UGC should ensure study leave with payment in whole private universities if publication is the requirement of promotion in university. Where is study leave act? Who should take care the study leave act in private universities? Study leave without pay is officially confusing the validity of a study leave letter, official research support, and promotion support. These are the facts and acts of official demotivation in higher education and City University.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek a fund to be a quality professor/quality practice of Bangladesh government.
- ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek an ethical recommendation of life safety support.
- ✓ UGC should verify and gazette Dr. Anowar's whole academic and professional profile and gazette his whole service for the government of Bangladesh (2006-2025) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).
- What is the action and support of UGC when Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is facing life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get a legal support to get PhD compensation award of Australian government of 230,72,50,000AUD. Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93,780AUD + compensation award of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87,560 AUD). RMIT University and Australian government should send the whole money to the bank account of Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.
- What is the action and support of Australian government when Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is facing life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get PhD compensation award of Australian government of 230,72,50,000AUD. Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93,780AUD + compensation of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87,560 AUD). RMIT University and Australian government should send the whole money to the bank account of Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.
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Anowar Hossain should get full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93, 780AUD + compensation of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87, 560 AUD). RMIT University and Australian government should send the whole money to the bank account of Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

- What is the action and support UN when Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is facing life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get PhD compensation award of Australian government of 230,72,50,000AUD. Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93, 780AUD + compensation of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87,560 AUD). RMIT University and Australian government should send the whole money to the bank account of Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.
- What is the action and support of professor community when Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is facing life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get PhD compensation award of Australian government of 230,72,50,000AUD. Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93,780AUD + compensation of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87,560 AUD). RMIT University and Australian government should send the whole money to the bank account of Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.
- What is the action and support of PhD supervisor at RMIT University when Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is facing life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school? What is the exact purpose of higher education? What is the exact purpose of PhD education? What is the situation of global academia? Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93,780AUD + compensation award of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87,560AUD).

3.13 UGC should monitor the private universities in Bangladesh and relevant facts in higher education, central policy making, and quality service

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is submitting his Postdoctoral thesis, PhD thesis, MTech (equivalent to MPhil/MSc degree) thesis, and BSc Engg thesis (2006-2025) to UGC for an anonymous assessment of Bangladesh government and/or international professor community (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) for the truthiness gazette of Bangladesh government. Dr. Anowar's

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International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

whole degree should be assessed by the UGC by the relevant professionals to ensure Dr. Anowar's professional service and/or professor practice in Bangladesh if UGC can issue a quality fund to the assessor and Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). What is the appointment policy of vice chancellor and chancellor of City University of Bangladesh? It should be well defined by the UGC. Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw very minor/zero advertisement in newspaper about the appointment of vice chancellor and chancellor of any university in Bangladesh. Every appointment of university should be transparent and legal. Every rules should be transparent and legal for the support of higher education. The number of private universities are higher than public universities in Bangladesh. But possibly there is no single UGC member from the private universities. What is the actual reason? What is the crime of private university teacher? UGC need to signify, clarify, and verify to the nation in front of professor community. What is the appointment process of UGC members? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain does not know. He also believes that majority of the teachers does not know. It seems that the private university teachers are comparatively disqualified and/or the crisis of the brand value of private universities in Bangladesh. UGC and education ministry should sanction quality research fund to the private university teachers. 50% PhD scholarship of UGC and government recommendation should be reserved and reserved for the private university teachers/students, without which the practice of private university should be banned in Bangladesh. Therefore, UGC and education ministry should satisfy the whole community of research and education in Bangladesh. A brand value crisis of Bangladeshi private university is critically remarked by the self-study of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. A researcher creates brand value of a university, but private university have no value/minimum value of a researcher category teachers. Still now, public university don't allow the graduate of private university to appoint as teacher. Sometimes, UGC also dislikes private universities and negatively advertises in the daily newspaper in Bangladesh for their self-protection and official existing of UGC. If UGC can not run the private universities, if UGC can not ensure the quality professor at private university, UGC should stop the private universities. If the government can not control the quality of private universities, if the UGC is afraid to private university, if the UGC is afraid to the trustee board of private university, UGC should stop the private universities (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Every university department should have 60-100% PhD/Postdoc category teacher. Some private university try to minimize departmental cost and try to keep 100% junior category teachers try to keep 100% lower paid teacher. Therefore, some senior teacher may have also seniority afraid to lose the job.

3.14 Salary structure, trustee board, philanthropist, and assessment of quality score of private university in Bangladesh

What is the funding principle of a funder to invest for a private university? The investment or donation of a founder of a private university should be well signified and clarified to the government to the citizen. The government invest in public university for the development of the country. What is the difference between the government funding in public university and private funding in private university? In general view, both funders should have the similar objectives to satisfy the quality education in Bangladesh. If there is a target of profit and loss, the private university should write private limited company after the name of the university. If the trustee and funder/founder/director are the same person of a private university, it seems that the private university is serving as private limited company. Practically the term of trustee board is introduced in Bangladesh in the different way of the organizational practice of two equal to five, organizational technique of two equal to five, vice chancellor, treasurer, and UGC. So, the word of trustee board will be invalid for the private limited company for the private university in Bangladesh. Accordingly, the trustee board law should be more respected, practiced, and scrutinized by the govern of the UGC and education ministry. The chairman and member of a trustee board should have a standard salary/consultancy fee should have an individual salary for their prestigious position if they have an active involvement with the private service of the private university. The financial contribution of a trustee board chairman should be well written, well narrated, and gazetted in the university profile and UGC profile for the motivation of education service and contribution to Bangladesh government to Bangladeshi citizen in terms of a philanthropist/charity person in education of the country. A person should not be a chairman of the trustee board by birth by family but the person may get a support of the employment if he/she needs in terms of funder/founder support. A philanthropist/charity person donates his/her money for the contribution of university education. For example; if a person has two billion BDT, he/she may donate one billion for the contribution of university education. A philanthropist/charity person will get government value as 'very important person (VIP)' person of the country. Bangladesh government and UGC can also maintain a bank account of post death philanthropist. A wealthy person can easily nominate his/her bank account for the education service of the government. For example: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can nominate one of his bank account for the education service of the government. By rules of the government, 25% of the post death wealth should nominate for the charity of the UGC for the charity of the government education and/or the percentage can be fixed in terms of the total property of the death person. For example, Mr. Khan Bahadur Ahsanullah was an Indian and Bengali philanthropist. Similarly, there were many known and unknown philanthropist who contributed their property/land for primary school education, high school education, college/university education in Bangladesh. University administration, researcher, scientist, professor, and the whole people of the university will officially acknowledge

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the VIP person for their tremendous contribution in university. A vice chancellor/chancellor/renowned person should not be a non-paid member/secretary for the service of the trustee board of any private university in Bangladesh. The salary structure/honorarium of a private university from office assistant to vice chancellor and chancellor should be well structured should be well monitored should be well advertised among the private universities, central administration of the government, and the UGC. Salary structure of an organization should not be top-secret. There is so many educated persons in Bangladesh who have no property by birth who invested for the self-education who can not lead quality life without their monthly earning. Moreover, the functions of the teachers/professors/scientists in the private university are remarkable for the total development of the country, total surviving the peoples, total peace of the country, and total impact for the global surviving. Moreover, there is so many philanthropists in Bangladesh who got huge wealth by birth who got huge wealth by corruption who got huge wealth by business. So, it should be well remarked to nominate a philanthropist of the UGC of the country of the government. A business class person may get more grade point to nominate a philanthropist of the UGC of the country of the government. Similarly, every higher educated person is also a philanthropist who donate his/her knowledge for the total development of the country without getting full reimbursement from the country with getting nominal salary/zero salary from the country. The salary structure/honorarium of a private university is a quality performance of the university. Every peer reviewer and quality score of a private university should signify, justify, notify, and assess accordingly. The administration of the University should not have a scope to satisfy peer reviewer by paying money. Therefore, a central meeting should be conducted by the UGC chairman to notify this message/letter to the chairman of the trustee board, vice chancellor, and chancellor of the whole private universities and public universities in Bangladesh. These should be the routine job of UGC chairman.

3.15 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) asking ‘education compensation award’ of City University, Bangladesh (standard salary of 63, 72, 463BDT + compensation of double salary = 12, 744,926BDT), and compensation support to Bangladesh government through UGC, table 1 & figure 3

At 38 to 45 ages, a defence soldier of Bangladesh government can go to retirement who get life time allowance for a specific time duration who serve after the study of secondary school/higher secondary school. A primary school teacher or high school teacher in village also get a salary who sacrifices for local college graduation and/or higher secondary education. A simple BSc graduate/MSc graduate in high school/college also earn extra money by teaching extra hours in Bangladesh, but a Professor (Dr.) in Textile Engineering can not earn extra money by writing

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

publication by investing extra hours in Bangladesh and Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also part of human being although he graduated from City University. An UGC nominated committee may assess the whole issue relates to promotion, PhD, and salary of City University (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) (Hossain, 2023b). City University should pay full term and full-time salary of Dr. Anowar under the repeated assessment of his 'PhD study leave' under the repeated assessment of right designation in the appointment process in 2017. Considering five years duration fixed deposit rate of First Security Islami bank, the salary of PhD study leave duration should be higher and/or almost double, City University should pay the standard interest rate to satisfy the financial achievement of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. City University should also calculate or pay the salary in terms of adjusting and considering the promotion and designation. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also submitted a letter of promotion at City University (Hossain, 2023b). Who should gazette to Dr. Anowar's promotion at City University? Who should take care Dr. Anowar's promotion at City University if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not ask to UGC if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not ask to City University? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also sacrificed his quality of life during his teaching at City University and PhD education at RMIT University. It was a wrong letter signed by the registrar against the PhD act, study leave (without pay) act, and higher education act and motivation of Bangladesh government, whatever practiced in different public universities in Bangladesh. Who should monitor the City University? Who should monitor the brand value of City University? (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) Who should supervise the City University? If the stomach of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is empty, if he has no money, if his lifestyle is poorer and poorer, how can he continue quality research, how can he serve for university, how can he serve for the country, how can he show his professional excellency to Bangladesh government through a private university, how can he be a quality professor? But presently he has no food in his stomach, he has no family life due to his financial crisis. But he has no car, he has no house, he can not access his research office at RMIT University without going to Australian court and/or international court. How can he write this letter to UGC without having his research office? Both former vice chancellor, present vice chancellor, concern head of the department of City University should be liable to ensure his salary and promotion at City University in Bangladesh if former vice chancellor got PhD salary during his study leave at Bangladesh Agricultural University, Bangladesh. If City University respect the PhD of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, City University should pay his salary of the whole study leave duration. How a university can stop the salary when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got international scholarship when he got valid study leave letter? How a university can issue/sign non-judicial study leave letter of without pay in Bangladesh? How a vice chancellor can allow or approve study leave without pay? How a registrar can sign or approve study leave without pay? May Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain seek ethical support of UGC to achieve his

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professional excellency. Chancellor and Vice Chancellor, City University, Bangladesh should take necessary action to assess and pay the full-term salary of 12, 744,926BDT to the bank account of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain briefly reported his PhD research at RMIT University to the chancellor and vice chancellor, City University, Bangladesh. So, City University should pay the full-term duration full salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Possibly, all public university teachers are getting salary during study leave in Bangladesh for the support of research and brand value of the university. Practically and officially, every private university salary should be double of public university. Private universities have no plan of retirement policy of a professor. Who should take the lifelong liability of a professor in private university? Which organization of Bangladesh should take this liability if UGC is serving for private universities in Bangladesh? What is the salary structure of primary school teacher in village area of Bangladesh government? What is the quality of a primary school teacher? What is the quality of a private university teacher in textile engineering? What is the salary structure of City University teacher of Bangladesh government (2017-2025)? Private university should follow the exact salary trend among primary school teacher, high school teacher, college teacher, and public university teacher. Private university creates societal imbalance and societal disturbance in the name of university teacher and university salary. Chairman of a private university teacher build the hill of money but the teacher of private university can not eat food. But the teacher can not talk to university due to job security due to the job threatening due to the private and private. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was a private university graduate in City University when he paid higher tuition fees when he paid twelve to twenty times higher than public university in Bangladesh. Oppositely, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was a private university teacher at City University when he got less than half salary compared to public university in Bangladesh. Possibly, this is his lifelong government penalty in Bangladesh to study at City University, possibly this is his lifelong crime in Bangladesh to study at private university, possibly this is his lifelong crime in Bangladesh to invest for the brand value of City University, possibly this is his lifelong government penalty on behalf of UGC of Bangladesh government. What was the reason of lifetime financial penalty to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain if he is a qualified teacher of City University? Who should take this responsibility of Bangladesh government? Who introduced City University in Bangladesh? Who gazetted City University in Bangladesh? Who pulled Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the City University in Bangladesh? Who invited Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the City University in Bangladesh? If City University can not respect and/or allow City University graduate, City University should be banned in Bangladesh. What is the study leave act in private university? What is the financial benefit of a private university teacher when he is studying and practicing PhD

research thousand and thousand hours as prerequisite of official PhD study leave of City University? UGC should signify, clarify, and notify the solution very clearly in front of the nation in front of the professor community in front of the global community. UGC should clarify to the global professor community. Who should take the responsibility? Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also attaching his bank statement of First Security Islami bank (FSIB) to satisfy the salary of City University in 2017-2020. City University should prove the legal right of City University teacher by paying the full-term full duration salary of study leave if City University is officially respecting the legal beauty of higher education, research, publication, PhD research, and UGC policy on behalf of higher education act of Bangladesh government, on behalf of Bangladesh government, on behalf of UGC, on behalf of chancellor and vice chancellor of City University in Bangladesh. May Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain seek UGC recommendation to pay the full-term duration full salary including PhD compensation package of study leave duration due to artificial financial crisis due to sacrifice of quality of life. UGC should recommend a standard salary structure for the teachers for the whole private universities in Bangladesh if private university teachers are also teacher of Bangladesh government. At least, the gross salary and retirement support should not be lower than public universities in Bangladesh. Who should be liable to take care the salary structure of private universities? Who should be liable to take care the financial audit of private universities? A compensation report of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University, Bangladesh has been represented for the rapid action and support of the director and chairman of UGC, and ministry of education. The post of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City university on 17 August 2017 should be assistant professor (grade-6) instead of lecturer (grade-9)(Hossain, 2023e). The consolidated salary of 25000BDT was paid to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain against the post of lecturer (textile engineering)(Hossain, 2023e). The consolidated salary is the wrong salary structure and wrong designation, signed by the registrar of City University. The consolidated salary of 25000BDT is less than half salary/gross facilities of a lecturer of a public university in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain taught full class room student in day section and evening section of City University. The seat and capacity of the student were full and occupied; the student seat was not vacant. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was unable to talk without speaker who asked electronic speaker support in the class room to the additional registrar of City University. Accordingly, the mark sheets records are reserved at the department of exam controller, City University for the reference of student numbers and student capacity (2017-2020). Similarly, the seat and capacity of the student were full and occupied when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was a graduate student of City University (2006-2010); possibly the student seat was not vacant in day and evening section of BSc in Textile Engineering. The relevant teaching experience at public universities in Bangladesh and relevant academic study experience of two years duration full-time Master of Technology in Textile Technology (submitted publication record) were not accepted and/or positively considered in the appointment process in

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the designation process at City University. It seems that the brand value of Rajshahi University, Chittagong University, and University of Calcutta were not accepted and/or considered in the appointment process in the designation process in the salary grading process at City University (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). What is the reason? What is the intention of a private university? Who should monitor? Who should responsible on behalf of Bangladesh government? Why should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain ask salary? Why should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain think about salary? Why should Dr. Anowar write this letter to UGC? The five different class loads for the post of lecturer were taken instead of four-class load for the post of assistant professor. The additional classes were also taken and paid 15000BDT per class as payment of lecturer category. The additional classes should be paid per class as payment of assistant professor category. Therefore, salary should be adjusted, the post should be adjusted, the study leave salary should be adjusted, the payment of additional classes should be paid, the whole payment of additional duties and responsibilities should be paid, and should be paid to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for the post of assistant professor (MTech and Post MTech publication, 2016)(M. A. Hossain, 2023cb), associate professor (PhD¹ publication, 2017-2019)(M. A. Hossain, 2023ca), and senior professor (PhD^{2,3} publication, Postdoc¹⁻⁴ publication 2020-2025) (M. A. Hossain, 2023g) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f) under the support of UGC approved salary structure if the City University is approved and guided by UGC of Bangladesh government if the private universities have no separate UGC in Bangladesh if the private universities have no separate education ministry of Bangladesh government (M. A. Hossain, 2023ah; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). So far Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain know that Bangladesh has single UGC and single education ministry. The scholarly practice and scholarly achievement of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain were not accepted and/or considered and/or motivated for the appointment, designation, salary structure, actual salary grade, sequential performance, and sequential promotion at City University. The office of UGC should be completely liable to reimburse the compensated salary to the bank account of Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. I, Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-paid to City University when Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was a graduate student of City University (M. A. Hossain, 2023b). Similarly, and professionally; Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was invested (lower salary than standard salary in Bangladesh) and sacrificed quality of life at same university at City University of Bangladesh. Every compensated salary should be double than the general standard salary of City University due to facing financial crisis and sacrificing quality of life as a prestigious teacher of university teacher. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get a compensation award when he didn't get salary at right moment at right time at right sequence to expense and invest for a quality service to City University for quality surviving to

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

explore his beauty of scholarly service. City University should pay scholarly compensation since 2017 to still now. Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was an assistant professor since 22 July 2015 at University of Rajshahi. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain successfully completed the scholarly requirement of assistant professor since 2015 under the involvement of research and development at University of Calcutta, India. Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain served 100% to City University. City University should pay 100% to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not self-invest for City University for lifelong. Bangladesh government/UGC should invest for City University. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain served and showed his academic and professional performance at City University, Bangladesh (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested and self-sacrificed the salary to establish the brand value of City University of Bangladesh since 2006/2010 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain notified and knocked to the promotion team/head of the department, dean of the science and engineering faculty, registrar, office of the registrar, pro vice chancellor, and vice chancellor of City University of Bangladesh government since 2019-2024 (M. A. Hossain, 2023ah). But Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get any response from the concern team and/or concern office of the university. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-financed and self-invested to study BSc Engg, MTech, Post MTech, PhD¹⁻³, and Postdoc¹⁻⁴ (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). City University should pay the compensation award of standard salary to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. So, Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not invest for any assessment process of City university. So, Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking legal support and/or academic support of Bangladesh government through the professor court of UGC. Table 1, the total non-paid salary of City University, Bangladesh is 63, 72, 463BDT, in words sixty-three lakh seventy-two thousand four hundred and sixty-three BDT only. Therefore, the 'education compensation award' of City University, Bangladesh (standard salary of 63, 72, 463BDT + compensation of double salary = 12, 744,926BDT) should pay to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to protect Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain from the private university trapping from the life time academic, professional, financial trapping of the UGC of the Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not invest life-time, he can not pay/invest tuition fees in the name of compensated salary when he is a professor of City University when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a graduate student of City University. Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested all of his money for City University and education; and presently his pocket and bank account are almost empty and empty (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is sacrificing and sacrificing his quality of life, food, and sex life/marriage life. The people of Dr. Anowar's society knows that Professor of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a teacher of City University, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar

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Hossain is a City University graduate, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a textile engineer. But he can not adapt and survive with the poor people in his village society like auto rickshaw puller, day labour, office assistants, vegetable shopkeeper and tea makers beside the local roads and other local professionals due to his financial crisis, professional harassment, private university harassment and trapping, and the long-term trapping of private university and/or City University of Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask to UGC for the protection of private university trapping. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain parallelly faced the trapping of RMIT University, trapping of City University, and professor trapping. How many trappings should he face in the same pipeline when he has no food for going to court? The trapping of City University is officially and jointly supported by the ministry of education of Bangladesh government and UGC of Bangladesh government. So, the UGC and Bangladesh government should take the liability when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested in profession since 24 September 2006 to still now. Nobody should cease the achieved money of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's knowledge industry, table 1 and figure 3. He will go to high court against UGC and City University instead of professor's court of UGC if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don't get the imbursement of his money to his Bangladeshi bank account under the recommendation of UGC.

Table 1. Name of compensated designation and compensated experience summery at City University, Bangladesh; total non-paid salary of City University, Bangladesh: 63, 72, 463BDT, in words sixty-three lakh seventy-two thousand four hundred and sixty-three BDT only (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Legally, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be financially solvent professor in Bangladesh and financially solvent textile engineer in Bangladesh. But who make him financially poor and financially poorer in Bangladesh, mentioned in figure 3.

Name of compensated designation and paid/non-paid salary (±BDT) in terms of public university in Bangladesh	From	To	Year of experience	Degree studied	Peer reviewed publications	Paid salary BDT/month at City University, Bangladesh	Compensated/ actual salary/month (± BDT) in terms of public university in Bangladesh
Assistant Professor (Textile Engineering),	22 July 2015	21 July 2019	4	PhD ¹ Tech	6	25,000 (22 August 2017-21)	67,010

grade-6; total actual salary: 15,41,230 total paid: 5,86,500 total non-paid 9, 54,730						August 2018) 25,000 (22 August 2018- December 2018) 27,500 (January 2018-21 July 2019)	
Associate Professor (Textile Engineering), grade-4; total actual salary: 42,74,733 total paid: 1,76,960 total non-paid: 40,97,733	22 July 2019	21 July 2024	5	PhD ² Tech	10	27,500 (22 July 2019- December 2019), 30,300 (January 2020), Non-paid February 2020 to July 2024	71,200
Senior Professor (Textile Engineering), grade-1; total actual salary: total paid: 0BDT total non-paid: 13, 20, 000	22 July 2024	still now	19 (professional involvement and investment of full-time research, publication, invention, peer review services, research teaching, and theory teaching since 24 September 2006)	BSc Engg (four years full time), MTech (two years full time), PhD ¹⁻³ Tech (five years full-time, five years part time), Postdoc ¹⁻⁴ (part time)	Total number of publications: 152 (including peer reviewed, and non-peer reviewed)	Study leave (non-paid) August 2024 to June 2025 (still now)	1, 20,000

Figure 3. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's salary was 25000BDT per months after achieving the quality of assistant professor (textile engineering), but the standard salary of a lecturer in public university is 53000BDT (tech and non-tech). What is the intention/practice of City University about salary of a teacher? City University of Bangladesh can not pay the lecturer (Technology) category salary of a lecturer (textile technology) under the valid administration of vice chancellor and chancellor of the university. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/vice chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer of prestigious university/research organization.

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self-invested textile engineer and self-funded professor in textile technology (2006-2025). An UGC approved and supported system of academic cheating and professional trapping are focusing and proving in private university, Bangladesh. Both salary structure and tuition fees should be approved and/or monitored by the UGC for the academic excellence in private university. Every private university student pays for the support of professor's salary and administrative cost, but the public university student need not to pay due to government funding and/or government subsidiary. What is the expense to study at private university and what is the salary of a lecturer at private university/City University. UGC should assess and monitor. So, who will ensure quality salary to the teachers of the private university? Who is taking, expensing, and controlling the tuition fees of the private university students? Who is the guardian of private university? Who should monitor the private university? This is not a packet of baby biscuit of five BDT, if the quality is bad, we can throw it to the dustbin. Bangladesh government may ensure a subsidiary of the salary of private university teacher's if necessary if Bangladesh government sees the public university and private university with a single eye without having different eye without having different angle of looking without showing afraid symptom to/from private university. Bangladesh government may also have a subsidiary plan to ensure the quality of the private universities if the private university is also a government-controlled university if the private university is not only a trustee board/chairman-controlled university. Private university provides shared/common/crowdy study place for the teachers, but the public university ensures single/separate study place for the teachers. A quit place, a bookshelf, and enough oxygen are also a teaching tool of a university professor. Private university ensures minimum teaching tools, but the public university ensures maximum teaching tools in Bangladesh. In general, it seems that private university faces financial crisis. Private university may have a tendency to appoint lower quality teacher/junior teacher rather than senior teacher who have relevant Master degree and PhD degree. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain recommends for the subsidiary support for the private universities in different ways, such as: machine, land, building, professor, etc. The whole private universities may also be planned for the public-private partnership. There is no chance to deny any responsibility of any party of the government. In general, research and publication are the prerequisite of university service and university promotion. Every university lecturer may get monthly research allowance (additional) if publication policy is valid for the promotion in private universities. Every university lecturer should get allowance of part-time research degree and/or full-time research degree. Every university lecturer may get an allowance of supervisor fees and/or supervisor searching and/or professor searching, and professor coordination allowance in home and abroad. Every university lecturer may get an allowance of research proposal development for a research degree. Therefore, every hour of a professor should consider for a quality fee and quality development of the

university. Every university post/service should have separate salary in private universities. Such as professor, head of the department, Dean of the school, pro vice chancellor, and vice chancellor. Some private university and colleges in Bangladesh have no separate salary for the different post who offer consolidated salary for the teaching position and administrative position. The total salary and/or consolidated salary are/is the lower salary of an academician, but the private university tends to profit margin, but the professor/lecturer self-invests for his lifelong surviving in the profession. Every private university should follow standard salary structure of university teachers under the guideline of UGC and Bangladesh government, if the private university teachers are the higher graded teacher/higher qualified teacher than primary school teacher, high school teacher, and college teachers in Bangladesh. University chancellor, UGC, and vice chancellor may take necessary action for the support of private universities in Bangladesh, if private universities are contributing for the total development of the country. A chairman of trustee board of private university should not dominate to the vice chancellor of the university to satisfy the intentional approach to vice chancellor. These are the symptom of judicial crimes. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain did self-funding PhD¹ in Textile engineering and research practice on behalf of Bangladesh and India. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also did self-invested PhD² in Textile engineering and research practice on behalf of Australian government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is officially submitting to the office of chairman, UGC for a quality assessment of his PhD degree and every protocol of the truthiness process of Bangladesh government (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g, 2023cf).

Figure 3. A comparison and confusing of teacher’s salary versus student’s tuition fees in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023ah, 2023ca).

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3.16 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) remarked the truthiness act, fact, wrong practice of UGC, Bangladesh, and harming/harmed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, if UGC harmed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, UGC may nominate him for the post of UGC chairman (one term duration) for the compensation support to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain did self-funding MTech in Textile Technology and research practice on behalf of Indian government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is officially submitting to the office of chairman, UGC for a quality assessment of his MTech degree (M. A. Hossain, 2023b, 2023ca). How can UGC write an equivalence certificate that the equivalence certificate is not ensuring the truthiness of the degree. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain paid an official fee to the UGC for the quality assessment when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted a printed copy of MTech thesis to UGC in 2017 as prerequisite of equivalence certificate of foreign degree of Bangladeshi UGC. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also submitted word/pdf file by pen drive to Mr. Jahirul Islam, Assistant, director, UGC. UGC may take a separate truthiness fee but the UGC should not write accordingly. If UGC is not assessing the truthiness, what is the necessity to make a remark about truthiness? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain applied for equivalence certificate; applicant didn't applied for truthiness certificate. Therefore, the edited equivalence act 2020 should also be modified. If UGC can not certify the truthiness, the equivalence process and equivalence certificate are invalid, unnecessary, and a ready question mark for the job searching process of the degree achiever. So, UGC should not write the word of truthiness in the equivalence certificate on behalf of Bangladesh government. These are the confusing word to assess a foreign certificate in Bangladesh to establish foreign degree in Bangladesh. Moreover, public university separately ask for equivalence certificate of the foreign degree in Bangladesh. It seems that UGC certificate of foreign degree equivalence is dishonored by the public university in Bangladesh. How can UGC issue a certificate in Bengali instead of international language? Every foreign equivalence should be in English. Who should monitor the UGC in Bangladesh? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a paid consultant and/or paid member of UGC. MTech degree of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is equivalent to MPhil degree in Textile Technology and/or MSc degree in Technology in Bangladesh. If Bangladeshi UGC can not certify truthiness of foreign degree, Bangladeshi UGC should not certify the equivalence of the foreign degree. To solve the truthiness, UGC may start a student filing process from the starting moment and ending moment of the foreign degree. Please assess the argument from the office of chairman, UGC. Every equivalence and truthiness are the process of international education act between two government.

If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submit a PhD certificate of RMIT University, still Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain need to get truthiness certificate of Bangladesh government. So, Bangladesh government may officially assess his PhD achievement, and Post doctoral achievement (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)(M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g) rather than PhD certificate. Therefore, may Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain seek a truthiness gazette of Bangladesh government under the truthiness assessment of MTech research achievement, PhD¹⁻³ research achievement, and Post-doctoral¹⁻⁴ research achievement. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was searching and searching the international education act of Bangladesh. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get accordingly. Possibly, Bangladesh government has limitation to develop and announce the international education act of foreign research degree and/or foreign research experience. So far Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain know, so far Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can understand, the foreign certificates and foreign scholarly achievements are being accepted in Bangladesh in Bangladeshi universities. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to ask officially to Bangladesh government if Bangladesh government or chancellor of universities can gazette the brand value of University of Calcutta in Bangladesh in terms of personal excellency and thesis (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz, 2023ca) of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to ask officially to Bangladesh government if Bangladesh government or chancellor of universities can gazette the brand value of RMIT University in Bangladesh in terms of personal excellency and thesis (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g) of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is submitting all of his academic and professional requirements for the official assessment and official gazette of professor community of Bangladesh government and/or chancellor of Bangladeshi universities. (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get legal affiliation of education service at reputed public university in Bangladesh, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have legal right to ask accordingly (M. A. Hossain, 2023cb). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain did self-funding engineering and research practice on behalf of Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is officially submitting to the office of chairman, UGC for a quality assessment and gazette of professor community of Bangladesh government of his BSc engineering degree and personal excellency (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also officially submitting to the office of chairman, UGC, Bangladesh for a quality assessment and gazette of his professional practice since 2006 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

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 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
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 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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People's Republic of Bangladesh Office of the Notary Public-Bangladesh

S.N. ISLAM & ASSOCIATE'S

Advocate & Notary Public (Whole Bangladesh)

According to the Section 8 (1)(h) of Notary ordinance 1961 Ad

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BMK/ Scholarship/2.164/SMT/Certificate/2013/Vol-12/3064

Date: 23 Bhadro 1424 / 17 Sept.2017

Subject: Equivalence of Degree earned from foreign University

In terms of the above, it is inform that, it is stated that in the 86th meeting of the Committee of Foreign Degree Equivalence of the Bangladesh University Grants Commission, the degree obtained from the foreign university of the applicant described below has been equated with the Bangladesh Degree mentioned in the reverse of its name.

S.L. No.	Name of the Degree and Father's Name	Name of the Degree University	Name of the Earned Degree	Equality of Bangladesh Degree
01	Md. Anwar Hossain S/O: Late Md. abdur Rashid	University of Calcutta, India	Master of Technology in Textile Technology	Master in Textile Engineering

The degree certified above does not guarantee the truth

with the approval of the authority
 Sd./Illegible
 07.09.2017
 Md. Samsur Alam
 Director
 Reaches Support and Public Division
 Phone: 8181618

26 NOV 2019

Md. Anwar Hossain
 S/O: Late Md. abdur Rashid
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Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

গণপ্রজাতন্ত্রী বাংলাদেশ সরকার
বাংলাদেশ বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় মঞ্জুরী কমিশন
 ইউজিসি ভবন, প্লট # ই-১৮/এ, আগারগাঁও প্রশাসনিক এলাকা
 শেরে বাংলা নগর, ঢাকা-১২০৭
 ফোন: ৮৮-০২-৮১৮১৬১৮, ফ্যাক্স: ৮৮-০২-৮১৮১২৮১
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২৩ ভাদ্র ১৪২৪
 ০৭ সেপ্টেম্বর ২০১৭

বিষয় : বিদেশী বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় থেকে অর্জিত ডিগ্রির সমতা বিধান।

উপর্যুক্ত বিষয়ের পরিপ্রেক্ষিতে জানানো যাচ্ছে যে, বাংলাদেশ বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় মঞ্জুরী কমিশনের বিদেশী ডিগ্রির সমতা বিধান কমিটির ৮৯তম সভার সুপারিশক্রমে নিম্নবর্ণিত আবেদনকারীর বিদেশী বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় থেকে অর্জিত ডিগ্রি তার নামের বিপরীতে উল্লিখিত বাংলাদেশের ডিগ্রির সাথে সমতা বিধান করা হয়েছে :

ক্র. নং	ডিগ্রি অর্জনকারীর নাম ও পিতার নাম	ডিগ্রি প্রদানকারী বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ের নাম	অর্জিত ডিগ্রির নাম	বাংলাদেশী ডিগ্রির সমতুল্য
১	২	৩	৪	৫
3064	Md. Anowar Hossain S/o. Late Md. Abdur Rashid	University of Calcutta, India	Master of Technology in Textile Technology	Master in Textile Engineering

উপরোক্ত প্রত্যয়ন প্রদত্ত ডিগ্রির সমতাতার নিশ্চয়তা বিধান করে না।

কর্তৃপক্ষের অনুমোদনক্রমে,
 মোঃ শামসুল আলম
 পরিচালক
 হিসার্চ সাপোর্ট এন্ড পাবলিকেশন ডিভিশন
 ফোনঃ ৮১৮১৬১৮

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 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
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97/TXM/130003 15/0033339 00002

University of Calcutta

This is to certify that
Md Anowar Hossain
 obtained the degree of *Master of Technology*
 in this University at the *Annual Examination*
 in the year **2015**, the special branch in which he
 was examined having been **Textile Technology**
 (**Technical Textiles**) and that he was placed
 in the **First Class**.

Senate House,
The 16th July, 2015

8800002

Sugata Marjit
Vice Chancellor.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

3.17 Promotion, performance, and motivation harassment to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University, Bangladesh and relevant crimes

Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, assistant professor got assistant professor post at City University without having teaching experience as lecturer. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got lecturer post having the industry experience in Bangladesh, having the public university experience in Bangladesh, having the public university experience in India (M. A. Hossain, 2023b, 2023br). It seems that the experience of Indian education and public university experience in Bangladesh have no value at City University. Somehow, he/committee dishonored/made small to the industry experience in Bangladesh, public university experience in Bangladesh, public university experience in India due to having textile engineering graduate at private university/City University of Bangladesh. These are the demotivation symptom to private university graduate at City University, Bangladesh. Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, City University showed administrative attitude to include name in the publication of PhD¹ (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz) in the publication of PhD² (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g) under the administrative force and scholarly crime of head of the department, seniority crime, and misguiding to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at the department (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). Parallely, Dr. AKM Saiful Islam demotivated tie fashion in the dress code at the City University office room and white color good looking shirt in the dress code at the dean office of City University during second meeting of nomination at City University (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024y). But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw a viva board of UGC that the UGC chairman was wearing white color shirt. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw that Indian PhD researcher was wearing white color shirt in front of the professor/supervisor. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw that professor of University of Calcutta, India; Bangladesh University of Textiles, Bangladesh; and RMIT University, Australia were wearing white color shirt in front of the colleagues/students. It seems that the white color shirt (M. A. Hossain, 2023as) and good-looking dress code are valid for the university dress code of Bangladesh government and/or professor community and/or student community. If UGC chairman of Bangladesh can wear white color shirt, why Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not wear white color shirt at City University when City University had/has no official dress code of the central administration. It seems that Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not wear good dress due to having private university degree, later he tried to wear poor quality dress. Possibly/psychologically, Dr. AKM Saiful Islam can not respect the graduate of City University/private university but he is earning from City University. It seems that Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not get the post of assistant professor/associate professor/professor due to having private university degree at City University. It seems that Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not get the post of assistant professor/associate professor/professor without ensuring publication benefit/scholarly benefit to Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, head of the department. These are the symptom of performance harassment to the central

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administration of City University, demotivation, and psychological harm to decline the professional growth and natural growth of personal excellency in student connections, and professional connections; and financial excellency of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University. Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman, Assistant Professor, City University was also unhappy due to PhD¹ publication and rapid performance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University. Parallely, Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman, coordinator of the department threatened to cease the job and made a beating threat at department due to having good performance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.). Parallely and psychologically, Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman negatively assessed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at the office of City University by looking the house condition of Dr. Anowar at village. These are the symptom of professional penalty at the department when Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman was not getting any profit from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain but Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman was getting a salary of assistant professor from City University. Moreover, Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman had a hidden connection with the family people/peoples of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman commented accordingly who forced to pay mother, tried to make the character of the social disorder in the name of mother in the teaching profession and showed seniority crime at the department (M. A. Hossain, 2023ba, 2023bb). Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman psychologically harmed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at the office of City University (2017-2020) and tried to harm the official performance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Moreover, Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman and Dr. AKM Saiful Islam jointly proposed the job of wife of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University. Officially, professionally, and personally; Dr. Anowar's mother and Dr. Anowar's wife were unknown to Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman and Dr. AKM Saiful Islam; Dr. Anowar's mother and Dr. Anowar's wife didn't go to office in Australia and Bangladesh; Dr. Anowar went to office in Australia and Bangladesh; Dr. Anowar was/is the employee at City University, Bangladesh; and RMIT University, Australia. But, Dr. AKM Saiful Islam didn't support promotion/salary and performance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the central administration of City University, but it was the major duty of Dr. AKM Saiful Islam at City University/private university (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). The performance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was better than Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman and Dr. AKM Saiful Islam; and it was the professional crime at department and major crime of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University, Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman and Dr. AKM Saiful Islam like second God (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). Under the discussion reference with Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman and Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, City University, 2022; possibly they had a

connection with Bangladeshi PhD researcher/person/relevant connection in Australia. Possibly, Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman had a connection with Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye/surrounding people/relevant connection with Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye under the discussion reference/comment of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye in a Microsoft team meeting where Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced a critical life-threatening conspiracy, hospital conspiracy, and family conspiracy in Australia and Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman and Dr. AKM Saiful Islam should have administrative punishment and penalty/compensation of 1000000BDT (in words ten lakh BDT) of each. The ‘compensation award’ of 1000000BDT should be paid to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. They should have academic punishment of two promotion drop (2018-) at UGC approved universities in Bangladesh and other universities (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

Somehow, the air of administrative conspiracy of City University and/or the chain of conspiracy naturally transferred to the Australian God father at RMIT University, Australia. It is also being cited the crimes and approached death penalty of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia due to having his criminal activities in Bangladesh and Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Although, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, and Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye like second God (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

Table 2. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is proposing and expecting relevant service post in terms of professional difficulties, professional harassment, private university harassment in Bangladesh, lifetime compensation, compensation award, lifetime safety, and recommendation of salary with safety allowance.

Name of expected post and organization	Name of expected post and organization	Duration	Compensation types, compensation awards, and relevant facts
President/ chancellor of Bangladesh government/ Bangladeshi universities (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x),	Chief Professor, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia and/or Chief Scientist of	Life-long	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD² schooling conspiracy in Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). ✓ Harassment in scholarly growth. ✓ To dedicate to increase the brand value of higher

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/vice chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer of prestigious university/research organization.

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 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
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<p>One term or five years</p>	<p>relevant research organization in Australia</p>		<p>education and research excellency in global platform.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RMIT University should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of RMIT university, moreover they hampered the quality of achievement of Dr. Anowar. ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment in Australia. ✓ Nobel nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get full term and full-time duration PhD scholarship since 6 July 2022 to still now (scholarship of 93,780AUD + compensation award of double value of PhD scholarship of RTP stipend scholarships at RMIT University, Australia = 1,87,560AUD).
	<p>Chief Professor, Bangladesh Textile University, Bangladesh and/or Chief Scientist of relevant research organization in Bangladesh</p> <p>Life time consultant or life time member of UGC, Bangladesh</p>	<p>Life-long</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faced private university harassment in professional climbing and government and non-government assessment in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ Faced harassment in government assessment of public university job such as Bangladesh Textile University, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, Jessore Science and

			<p>Technology University (M. A. Hossain, 2023as).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faced harassment in assessment of industrial job, daily earning, and daily food management for a private university affiliation of Bangladesh government and UGC (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD² schooling conspiracy in Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). ✓ Harassment in scholarly growth. ✓ To dedicate to increase the brand value of higher education and research excellency in global platform. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment in Bangladesh.
	Vice Chancellor or Chancellor, City University, Bangladesh	One term or 5 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-funding and scholarly investment in academic and professional journey, invested for the brand value of City University (2006-2025). ✓ Non-standard salary structure of UGC ✓ Faced private university harassment in the name of City University in professional

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			<p>climbing in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Sacrificed marriage life due to professional harassment. ✓ As 4th batch graduate of the department, self-invested to develop city university branding since 2006. ✓ Faced harassment in assessment of industrial job in textile industry and earning for a private university affiliation in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ In terms of salary and designation at City University had no value of Dr. Anowar's certified degree of two years duration full-time Master of Technology in Textile Technology by research from University of Calcutta (M. A. Hossain, 2023ah). Every academic experience should be equivalent to professional experience. Every professional experience should have a value in academic job and salary. Every academic experience should have a value in academic job and salary. Demotion of previous designation/dishonored three public university experiences during appointment, non-standard salary, non-paid salary of study leave duration,
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			<p>and demotivation to PhD research in Australia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ City university graduate should have a priority in city university appointment process in terms of competitive assessment and compensation package/salary. ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD² schooling conspiracy in Australia. ✓ To dedicate to increase the brand value of City University (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is writing the name of City University in his nameplate, City University should be public funded university and/or City University should get enough fund from the UGC and/or education ministry of Bangladesh government. City University should start PhD program and/or research program. City University should be globally traded as research university. ✓ City University should have all qualifications of international standard university. Accordingly, UGC should make necessary action and support to make a quality university of Bangladesh government. Without which, the education service of City University should be
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			<p>banned/stopped in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain can not take lifelong liability of City university brand harassment under the official support of UGC under the official support of Chancellor of City University, Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is a person. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is not an organization. UGC should not deny their responsibilities in terms of a busy organization.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ City University should pay earned money and compensation award of 12, 744,926BDT (in words: one crore twenty seven lakh fourty four thousand nine hundred and twenty six BDT only) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g, 2023ah, 2023bz, 2023ca; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024x).
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	Vice Chancellor or Chancellor, University of Calcutta, India	One term or 5 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-funding and scholarly investment. ✓ Invested professional experience and self-funded served to Calcutta University by research and publication. ✓ Self-sacrificed two years duration full-time professional earning. ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD² schooling conspiracy in Australia. ✓ University of Calcutta should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of University of Calcutta (M. A. Hossain, 2023ca). ✓ To dedicate to increase the brand value of University of Calcutta for the global reputation(M. A. Hossain, 2023ca).
	Vice Chancellor or Chancellor, RMIT University, Australia	One term or 5 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faced life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school at RMIT University (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc). ✓ Tried to cease scholarly invention and scholarly climbing in Australian PhD school. ✓ Invested professional experience and full-time served to RMIT University by

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			<p>research and publication (M. A. Hossain, 2023g).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-funding and scholarly investment (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). ✓ Sacrificed quality of life due to professional harassment. ✓ Sacrificed marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ Harassment in PhD achievement. ✓ Sacrificed marriage life due to family harassment in Australian PhD school. ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD schooling conspiracy in Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). ✓ RMIT University should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of RMIT university, moreover they hampered the quality achievement of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g). ✓ To dedicate to increase the brand value of RMIT University for global reputation (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment.
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	<p>Vice Chancellor or Chancellor, University of Dhaka and/or Bangladesh Textile University and/or Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology and/or other relevant technological universities</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faced private university harassment in professional climbing and assessment in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ Faced harassment in government or UGC representative assessment of public university job such as Bangladesh Textile University, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, Jessore Science and Technology University (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was unable to meet with vice chancellor, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology in 2016-2017 because of private university graduate in Bangladesh. ✓ Faced harassment in assessment of industrial job, daily earning, and food management for a private university affiliation of Bangladesh government. ✓ Faced harassment (two times) in government assessment of UGC scholarship to pursue offered (two times) PhD at Herriot Watt University, UK, 2018-2019(M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD² schooling conspiracy in Australia.
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Every private university student/teacher may get job support in public university when a lot of public university graduates are doing job in private universities. ✓ Private universities are accepting the graduates of public universities in Bangladesh, but the public universities are neglecting and possibly 100% neglecting the graduates of private universities in the appointment process. The situation is embarrassing and discrimination in the government policy in the professor court or assessment process. UGC should have an act. ✓ At least one graduate should get official recommendation for the service to public university as official example of UGC as official function of UGC as official responsibility of UGC when UGC is granting the private university to ensure quality higher education. ✓ If UGC self-neglect the graduates of private universities, if private university self-neglect the graduate of private universities, let's shut down the whole private universities in Bangladesh, let's include the
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			<p>whole private universities with the public universities. Without which UGC should officially prove the equivalent quality and equivalent acceptance in Bangladesh. Who should take care the exact liability? It seems that the students are taking the liabilities but the UGC is not taking the practical liabilities, officialities, and professionalities. By the legal act, 50% post should be reserved for the private university graduate should get appointment in the government job. Without which, let's shut down the whole private universities in Bangladesh if private universities are not contributing for the government.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ To dedicate to increase the value of higher education and research for global reputation. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment.
	<p>Education Minister of Bangladesh (non-political category, to enhance quality of</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faced private university harassment in professional climbing and assessment in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as).

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	<p>higher education under special recommendation) or life time consultant of education ministry</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The government officially neglected to ensure action and support to assess life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024k). ✓ Self-funding and scholarly investment in scholarly convincing in 2022-2025. ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD schooling conspiracy in Australia. ✓ To dedicate to increase the value of higher education and research in Bangladesh. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university. ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ UGC and ministry of education should jointly pay the penalty/compensation award of 20000000BDT (in words: two crore BDT) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024k, 2024x).
	<p>Education Minister of Australia (non-political category,</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The government officially neglected to ensure action and support to assess life-

	<p>to enhance quality of higher education under special recommendation) or life time member of education department</p>		<p>threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024e).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-funding and scholarly investment in scholarly convincing in 2022-2025. ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD schooling conspiracy in Australia. ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ To dedicate to increase the value of higher education and research in Australia. ✓ A compensation award of 10000 Australian penalty unit should pay to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain(M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)
	<p>Chairman, UGC, Bangladesh</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faced private university harassment in professional climbing and official assessment in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ The UGC officially neglected to ensure the action and support to assess life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k). ✓ Self-funding and scholarly investment in scholarly

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			<p>convincing in 2022-2025 to the administration of Bangladesh and Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ To ensure safety in Bangladesh and Australia in terms of PhD² schooling conspiracy in Australia. ✓ Faced official harassment (two times) in government assessment of UGC scholarship to pursue offered PhD at Herriot Watt University, UK, 2018-2019 (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ In a PhD scholarship viva board in 2018-2019, an UGC member officially neglected the offer letter of Herriot Watt University, UK. She officially told, “Herriot Watt University is selling certificate.” (M. A. Hossain, 2023as) ✓ In another PhD scholarship viva board in 2018-2019, an UGC chairman officially neglected the professional practice at Newcastle university college, University of Chittagong, Bangladesh. Chairman officially denied the existing of Newcastle university college at University of Chittagong about awarding BSc engineering degree in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as).
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Certified equivalence of MTech degree without truthiness and/or remarked truthiness of UGC (M. A. Hossain, 2023br). ✓ To dedicate to increase the value of higher education and research. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ UGC and ministry of education should jointly pay the penalty/compensation award of 20000000BDT (in words: two crore BDT) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k, 2024x).
	<p>Chief Consultant/ Member of Bangladesh Textile Mill Association (BTMA)</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ BTMA affiliated textile industries evaluated City University, but they forgot to evaluate the graduate of City University. Therefore, they neglected City University graduate in textile industry (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage

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			<p>life/sex life due to professional harassment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ They neglected the plan of central government of Bangladesh ✓ They neglected the higher education project of Bangladesh government and/or UGC. They dishonored the investment or printed money of Bangladesh government. ✓ They neglected the scholarly investment of the textile engineering graduate (M. A. Hossain, 2023ca) ✓ They are running factory without textile graduate in Bangladesh. They are directly disrespecting the textile graduates. These are the symptom of failing in international competition of global market. Every textile industry should be full of textile graduate. These are the relevant job and relevant practice chamber of textile graduate. ✓ They neglected office order of president office and/or Bangladesh government and/or UGC decision and/or ministry of education and/or vice chancellor & chancellor of City University, Bangladesh. ✓ They neglected office order of political government in Bangladesh.
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ BTMA/textile ministry should have five official members, Professor (Dr.) category members who should have academically and professionally recognized in textile engineering under the ministry of education, government of Bangladesh. ✓ Textile engineers may be properly distributed to textile industries under the support, examination, and affiliation of textile ministry. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz).
	<p>Chief Executive Officer and/or Chief Consultant; Mascom Composite ltd.; Radix Ltd. Surabari, Kashimpur-6591, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh.</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ They evaluated City University, but they forgot to evaluate graduate of City University. Therefore, they neglected City University graduate(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Mr. Shams Uddin Ahmed, Chairman negatively criticized the brand value of City University(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ They didn't provide compensation of salary in profession (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to chairman like second God.

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Mascom composite PLC should pay the penalty/compensation award of 200000 BDT (in words: two lakh BDT) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024x) ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ They have lack of compliance support to textile engineers (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024x). ✓ They neglected the plan of central government of Bangladesh ✓ They neglected the higher education project of Bangladesh government and/or UGC. They dishonored the investment or printed money of Bangladesh government. ✓ They neglected the scholarly investment of the textile engineering graduate (M. A. Hossain, 2023ca) ✓ They are running factory without textile graduate in Bangladesh. They are directly disrespecting the textile graduates. These are the symptom of failing in international competition of global market. Every textile industry should be full of
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			<p>textile graduate in terms of quality manpower. These are the very relevant job and practice house of textile engineering graduate.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ They neglected the office order of president office and/or Bangladesh government and/or UGC decision and/or ministry of education and/or vice chancellor & chancellor of City University, Bangladesh. ✓ BTMA/textile ministry should have five official members, Professor (Dr.) category members who should have academically and professionally recognized in textile engineering. ✓ Textile engineers may be properly distributed to textile industries under the support/affiliation of textile ministry. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz).
	<p>Chief Executive Officer and/or Chief Consultant;</p> <p>Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group 297, Khartail, Sataish, Gazipura, Gazipur-1704, Dhaka, Bangladesh.</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ They evaluated City University, but they forgot to evaluate graduate of City University. Therefore, they neglected City University graduate (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ They have lack of compliance salary to textile engineers (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

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CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar, Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
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			<p>The administration took one month salary compensation against the notice period of resignation letter; how can Dr. Anwar manage his food and living cost of next month? But the organization didn't ensure compliance salary/exact compensation of textile engineering graduate/performance-based increment to a textile engineer (M. A. Hossain, 2023br). Moreover, Mr. ASM Shofiqus Salek (Chatak), Production Manager unofficially connected with mother/commented about the payment of mother but he parallelly and unethically monitored the performance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain but he parallelly and unethically tried to make sex harassment and psychologically harm to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain respected to manager and chief executive officer like second God (M. A. Hossain, 2023as).</p> <p>✓ Viyellatex PLC should pay the penalty/compensation award of 300000 BDT (in words: three lakh BDT) to Professor Dr.</p>
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			<p>Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ They neglected the scholarly investment of the textile engineering graduate (M. A. Hossain, 2023ca) ✓ BTMA/textile ministry should have five official members, Professor (Dr.) category members who should have academically and professionally recognized in textile engineering. ✓ Textile engineers may be properly distributed to textile industries under the support and affiliation of textile ministry. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz).
	<p>Chief Executive Officer and/or Chief Consultant;</p> <p>Niagara Textiles PLC; Chandra Circle, Kaliakair-1750, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh.</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ They evaluated City University, but they forgot to evaluate graduate of City University. Therefore, they officially neglected City University graduate (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Psychologically and professionally harmed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at Niagara Textiles PLC due to having a

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 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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			<p>City University graduate in Textile Technology (M. A. Hossain, 2023as).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engr. Pobitro Kumar Saha, Production Manager (Dyeing) negatively criticized the brand value of City University in Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Engr. Abu Baker Siddique, Production Manager (Dyeing) negatively criticized the brand value of City University in Bangladesh. (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to managers like second God. ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed quality of life, marriage life/sex life due to professional harassment. ✓ They neglected/dishonored the plan of central government of Bangladesh ✓ They neglected the higher education project of Bangladesh government and/or UGC. They dishonored the investment or printed money of Bangladesh government. ✓ They neglected office order of president office and/or
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			<p>Bangladesh government and/or UGC decision and/or ministry of education and/or vice chancellor & chancellor of City University, Bangladesh.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ BTMA/textile ministry should have five official members, Professor (Dr.) category members who should have academically and professionally recognized in textile engineering. ✓ Textile engineers may be properly distributed to textile industries under the support and affiliation of textile ministry. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university. ✓ Niagara Textiles PLC should pay the penalty/compensation award of 100000BDT (in words: one lakh BDT) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)
	<p>Chief Consultant and/or Minister of Ministry of Textiles (special recommendation without democratic appointment)</p>	<p>One term or 5 years</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ BTMA affiliated textile industries evaluated City University, but they forgot to evaluate the graduate of City University. Therefore, they neglected City University graduate. ✓ They neglected the plan of central government of Bangladesh ✓ They neglected the higher education project of

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			<p>Bangladesh government and/or UGC. They dishonored the investment or printed money of Bangladesh government.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ They are running factory without textile graduate in Bangladesh. They are directly disrespecting the textile graduates. These are the symptom of failing in international competition of global market. Every textile industry should be full of textile graduate for the global surviving. These are the relevant job of textile graduate. ✓ They neglected office order of president office and/or Bangladesh government and/or UGC decision and/or ministry of education and/or vice chancellor & chancellor of City University, Bangladesh. ✓ BTMA/textile ministry should have five official members, Professor (Dr.) category members who should have academically and professionally recognized in textile engineering. ✓ Textile engineers may be properly distributed to textile industries under the support and affiliation of textile ministry. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate
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			private university(M. A. Hossain, 2023bz).
	Vice Chancellor or Chancellor of University of Rajshahi	One term or 5 years	<p>✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested & self-served to University of Rajshahi under the consolidated salary of affiliated college. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested to serve Bangladesh government at University of Rajshahi. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain certified the students of University of Rajshahi. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was the teacher of University of Rajshahi. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get right compliance support/salary of University of Rajshahi. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have legal right to ask to reimburse his compensation when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain served University of Rajshahi. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be one-term vice chancellor of University of Rajshahi. Without which, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask high court, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask UGC who are granting and granting the</p>

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			<p>private universities/colleges in Bangladesh who are parallely confusing and confusing the dream of students and teachers. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain certified the students, nobody should stop the colleges without valid reason of Bangladesh government, nobody should have right to stop the college. The college should be the department of University of Rajshahi, fully funded/partially funded by the government of Bangladesh. Without which students may be demotivated and students may lose their professional identity for their professional excellency when the students have no crime when the administration is doing crime. Still now, Bangladesh has huge lack of textile engineering graduates if UGC/education ministry/textile ministry can ensure the proper guideline to textile industry to BTMA and quality enhancement support.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Affiliated college didn't provide the salary structure of University of Rajshahi. ✓ Non-standard salary structure of UGC/ University of Rajshahi /affiliated college (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024x).
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ They didn't provide compensation of salary in profession (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to chairman/principal/professor of the college like second God. ✓ University of Rajshahi should pay the penalty/compensation award of 600000 BDT (in words: six lakh BDT) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) ✓ University of Rajshahi and UGC should be jointly liable to reimburse the standard salary to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain if he sincerely served for the government (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). UGC should not deny the government liability when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is facing a trapping of private university/college. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz).
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	Vice Chancellor Or Chancellor Of University of Chittagong	One term or 5 years	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested & self-served to University of Chittagong under the consolidated salary of
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			<p>affiliated colleges. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested to serve Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain certified the students of University of Chittagong. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was the teacher of University of Chittagong. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get right compliance support/salary of University of Chittagong. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have legal right to ask to reimburse his compensation when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain served to University of Chittagong. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be one-term vice chancellor of University of Chittagong. Without which, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask high court, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask UGC who are granting and granting the private universities/colleges in Bangladesh who are parallely confusing and confusing the dream of students and teachers. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain certified the</p>
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			<p>students, nobody should stop the college without valid reason of Bangladesh government, nobody should have right to stop the college. The college should be the department of University of Chittagong, fully funded/partially funded by the government of Bangladesh. Without which students may be demotivated and students may lose their professional identity for their professional excellency. Still now, Bangladesh has huge lack of textile engineering graduates if government can ensure the proper guideline to textile industry to BTMA, and quality enhancement support.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-funding and scholarly investment in academic and professional journey ✓ Non-standard salary structure of UGC/ University Chittagong/affiliated college(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). ✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain respected to chairman/principal/professor of the college like second God. ✓ University of Chittagong should pay the penalty/compensation award of 600000 BDT (in words: six lakh BDT) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Chairman of UGC harassed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain about the affiliated college of University of Chittagong in the viva board of PhD scholarship at UGC (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). ✓ University of Chittagong and UGC should be jointly liable to reimburse the standard salary to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain if he sincerely served for the Bangladesh government (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024x). UGC should not deny the government liability when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is facing a lifelong trapping of private university/colleges. ✓ Bangladesh government should officially prove/respect the brand value of a graduate of private university (M. A. Hossain, 2023bz).
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3.18 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) asked compensation support to UGC, Bangladesh

Table 2, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain would like to serve through the posts if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is eligible. Bangladesh government and Australian government may assess his whole achievement to assess and recommend a prestigious post under the special order under the special gazette of Bangladesh and Australia. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain get prestigious post in Bangladesh, Bangladesh will not be poor, Bangladesh will be richer and richer, Bangladesh will be reputed and reputed, Bangladesh will get more value in global platform and global competition. UGC should make a comment and administrative contribution to national and global issue of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar

Hossain, Defence Scientist. UGC should not deny the responsibility. UGC should have full of PhD expert, recorded PhD expert who have national and international reputation in PhD supervision and PhD research. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get a free of cost consultancy support. Everyone should get free of cost consultancy support in terms of public service of UGC. Without which, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain need to imagine that UGC serves for the government universities, UGC don't serve to private universities, UGC don't care about private universities. So, UGC should think or assess or recommend or fund about the separate UGC for private universities. UGC funds or recommends for public university. UGC don't fund or little fund to private universities. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek a quality placement support and/or Vice Chancellor and/or Chancellor of a renowned public university under the safety of Bangladesh government under the legality of private universities on behalf of UGC if UGC equally respect the private university and public university under the approved education act of Bangladesh government. UGC should prove, show, motivate, lead, and recommend accordingly. Private universities are being highly neglected for the scientist support, research support, scholarship support of higher education from UGC. Who will follow-up if there is no separate UGC for private universities? The rules of maximum private universities are very restricted, they can not follow or allow bamboo showing policy or crowdy policy, they can not follow crowdy policy of student community, they can not follow crowdy policy of professor community. Where is the promotion act of professor in Bangladesh? (Hossain, 2023b) Where is the PhD act in Bangladesh? Where is the study leave act in Bangladesh? Who should responsible? Who should guide if UGC is a very busy organization in Bangladesh if UGC is leading for quality education? Moreover, Australia has so many legal acts, so many education acts but they don't respect the legal act, but they don't care the legal acts and facts, but they don't implement the legal acts properly and properly. Possibly, Australian PhD school prioritizes sex rather than PhD act. So, what is the situation in global academia in PhD academia? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is afraid about the global education scenery. What is the exact purpose of education? Sometimes, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is being confused and confused. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also wrote to the secretary general of UN, prime minister of Australia, education department of Australia, and relevant executive authority of Australian government. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is advertising for zero crime in PhD school. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is advertising for zero crime for global surviving. PhD scientist, defence scientist, and Nobel prize are not personal wealth of anyone, these are the national and global development theory for the peace of mankind, these are the global surviving policy (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). So, these are the symbol of honour and honour. Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not getting any thesis of Nobel prize in the website of Nobel organization and/or online publication. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to visit Nobel prize organization to see the thesis of Nobel prize if Bangladesh can also

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 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
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International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, B.Tech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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approve or fund for an ‘international museum of Nobel prize thesis’. This is also part of Dr. Anowar’s ongoing research as Nobel nominee of RMIT University at RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also seeking a fund from Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, chief advisor of present government, chief advisor of Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have an affiliation of City University, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a member of City University, Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a right to get right direction from UGC. There is no professor in his department at City University. Who should appoint professor at City University? Should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain appoint professor at City University? So, UGC should take the full responsibility, full liability and full legality on behalf of Bangladesh government. University granting is the only responsibility of the UGC, university running and monitoring should also the responsibility of the UGC. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not self-finance lifetime to City University when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have also personal limitation have also financial crisis. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not self-finance lifetime to be a quality professor or quality scientist. Personally, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not appoint or self-fund to a professor to be a quality professor. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to be a quality professor. By this meaning, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also wrote to chancellor and vice chancellor of City University of Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t get any feedback from chancellor and vice chancellor of City University. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also wrote to chief advisor, foreign ministry, and chairman of UGC of Bangladesh government (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k). Everyone should take care of his legal appeal in terms of ethical beauty and glory of higher education (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k).

3.19 Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is lobbying for twin Nobel prize^{1,2} in camouflage physics (M. A. Hossain, 2023g) and peace (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

Due to having City University graduate in Bangladesh, personal excellency of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not be demotivated or harassed under the legal assessment of Bangladesh government under the assessment of UGC under the ethical assessment of Bangladeshi universities under the assessment of professor community in Bangladesh. Possibly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain need a prestigious post to claim to announce to win Nobel prize. A prestigious post should not be requirement for a Nobel prize. Highest administrative post of a country and/or professor are the requirement for the Nobel prize. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw in the website of Nobel organization/relevant site. Practically, a prestigious post should not be the requirement to win a Nobel prize. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also officially and professionally lobbying with UGC chairman, vice chancellor community,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

chairman community, president and prime minister of different countries, chief advisor of Bangladesh government, national and international professor community, Nobel winners and secretary general/president of UN (Hossain, 2023a, 2023d, 2024c, 2025). But personally, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain do not like lobbying. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get any PhD award of UGC (two times) in Bangladesh due to having City University graduate and/or City University teacher. These are the serious symptom UGC demotivation, UGC discrimination, professor trapping of UGC, and UGC harassment to the registered teacher of City University/private university. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get any financial support to be a quality professor in Bangladesh (2006-2025). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also need a quality position in Bangladesh to serve the country to eliminate the professional harassment to increase the personal safety. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also need a quality position in Bangladesh to win Nobel prize. Chairman of UGC is being requested to assess accordingly on behalf of Bangladeshi professor community. Hence, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to dedicate for Bangladesh government. Hence, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to dedicate or invest for his professional excellency for Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to seek safety recommendation of UGC if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is eligible as a private university teacher and/or graduate of City University (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Every safety is expensive all over the world. Professor has no security person; professor has no private secretary in Bangladesh and Australia. So, the total salary of a university professor should be higher than any other profession. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also writing this letter from the self-funded office and self-funded allowance. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have no food safety, how can Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invest for his personal safety, how can Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invest against international criminal? This is the critical moment of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

3.20 Who should get honorary doctorate degree of university? Who should get Nobel prize?

University is a place of scholarly practice and scholarly achievement. A person who can convince the committee by self-writing of self-contribution. Every university should patronize for global platform and global quality of achievement to ensure the right value of honorary. Every honorary degree/Nobel prize should have a thesis of self-writing and self-contribution. Honorary degree and Nobel prize are a matter of focusing self-contribution and self-writing for a specific field of contribution. Honorary degree and Nobel prize are not only a matter of focusing the impact factor by the support of journalist in daily newspaper and/or relevant support (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

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3.21 Second God and God father of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) in academic and profession in Australia and Bangladesh

In every organization, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain showed high performance and respected the supervisors/seniors/executive leaders as second God. Still, he faced unethical assessment of the second God. Still, the second God performed the duty as God father. It seems that supervisor and directorial concerns of the organization performs as God father of the organization. They always try to implement unethical technique for their personal benefit for their additional benefit from the subordinate employees/colleagues. God father harms to the organization and country for their personal benefit, additional earning, and personal climbing. God father don't care about the benefit of subordinate employees/colleagues. God father don't care about the performance/promotion of subordinate employees/colleagues. God father don't care about the benefit of organization. Parallely, they take salary from the organization from the employer. God father applies multidimensional techniques and weapon; and serves against the peace of subordinate employees/colleagues/organization. Sometimes, God father tries to hide his/her criminal activities by showing religious dress code, religious face code, religious talking, religious blackmail, and religious practice in the administrative office. God father also tries to make unethical harassment in the name of mother in the name of wife in the name of sex/biological issues (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024s) in the name of family connection (M. A. Hossain, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc) in the name of threatening in the name of life-threatening conspiracy in the name of beating in the name of psychological attack in the name of workloads in the name of private university harassment in Bangladesh in the name of dress code harassment (M. A. Hossain, 2023as) in the name of multidimensional facts. An Australian God father (M. A. Hossain, 2023as) threw administrative conspiracy and weapon of bullet and atomic bomb to the profession of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc). Possibly, God fathers like scholarly gift, financial gift, sex gift, and relevant gift for their additional benefit. Sometimes, God father has no ending point of their thinking, asking, and achieving of the illegal benefit. God father likes unethical benefit and God father may forget about their genuine benefit in their life cycle. Naturally, God father flies and flies like powerful aircraft, and run and run to the death point of their life cycle and lose every benefit. So, what is the benefit to be a God father? Every man should be a man. A man should not be a second God or God father. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking the support of Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j), Bangladesh (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k), and united nations (Hossain, 2025b) to achieve to reimburse to survive his lifelong academic and professional compensation for the peace of mankind.

4 Conclusion

Chairman, UGC; vice chancellor and chancellor of City University may extend relevant action and support on behalf of the Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking right support to the foreign ministry and education ministry of Australian government and Bangladesh government. Since 6 July 2022, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have no accommodation support, fooding support, office support, and transport support when he is writing this letter to the office of UGC of Bangladesh government. All concern professionals and organizations, political government, and non-political government are being requested to extend their ethical service to eliminate lifelong professional hassle and discrimination to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.). UGC and ministry of education should jointly solve the issue of private university, the issue of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without which UGC and ministry of education should pay the penalty/compensation award of 20000000BDT (in words: two crore BDT) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without which the salary of ministry of education and UGC should be stopped (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k, 2024x). If ministry of textiles can not run the textile industries of Bangladesh with textile engineering graduate, the salary of ministry of textiles should be stopped. By birth, every citizen is the contributor and beneficiary of the government wealth. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be one of them although he is a private university graduate/City University graduate of Bangladesh. Nobody should cease the birth right of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask printed money of Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have legal right to ask living and fooding support to Bangladesh government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get a recommendation of Nobel prize² in peace (M. A. Hossain, 2023f) for his private university harassment in Bangladesh (2006-2025), professional demotivation of Bangladesh, harassment in professional climbing in Bangladesh, financial demotivation at City University, and job harassment in the government organizations and non-government organizations (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

Your Honour, Please Pardon me

Best Regards for your excellency for the peace of mankind for the peace in higher education and research

23 June 2025

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(Md. Anwar Hossain)

Signature

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, BSc Engg, MTech, PhD & Postdoc; Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)

Office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain

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Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia; Nationality, National ID (Membership ID of Prime minister selection committee and president selection committee of Bangladesh government), Passport and Birth Registration Number: Bangladeshi (by birth), 19862692620993890, A15988852 (Present)/ EE0444946/AF3831770 (previous), 003236.

Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc; Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>

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Page | 91

For showing my honour, for the excellency of PhD schooling and human being all over the world; may Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also forward (randomly sequenced) a copy of this letter for their excellency

The whole incidence is being kept and recorded in online platform for the peace of PhD schooling for the peace of professor community for the peace human being all over the world.

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Abbreviations and glossaries

BDT: Bangladeshi taka

BSc Engg: Bachelor of Science in Engineering

BTMA: Bangladesh Textile Mill Association

E-mail: electronic mail

God father: an informal and philosophical meaning of comparison to signify the power like unseen God of the religious peoples. God father practices crimes and having expertise to hide the crimes.

MTech: Master of Technology

Private university harassment: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) faced harassment in Bangladesh for the affiliation of a private university in Bangladesh.

PhD: Doctor of Philosophy

Professor trapping: an unethical controlling and artificial demotivation are called trapping in academia which may generate chain trapping, chain crime, and chain demotivation. A professor can not appoint a paid assistant for the support of publication writing, but the professor may harass to other colleagues for the support of publication writing for the support of promotion. Professor trapping is very dangerous than general trapping (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain,

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2024x). The crime of professor trapping should be higher than general trapping. Nationally and internationally, these are the challenging facts in academia in professor community.

RMIT: Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology

Second God: an informal and philosophical meaning of comparison to signify the power like unseen God of the religious peoples.

UN: united nations

UGC: university grants commission

USD: United States dollar

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International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 engg), applied law & criminology
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 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
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 BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence
 research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime,
 crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high
 court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king
 of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament,
 government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education,
 research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal
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official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
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 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an*

- international standard University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection* [Biodata]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024aa). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government* [Grant]. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening*

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245079>

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. K. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-cost-minimization-process-of-heat-and-energy-for-Hossain-Samanta/145246a45b40a7ef33c3e37cc99083f91f6555fa>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, D. S., Barrister (Dr.). (2025). *Journal of Dr. Anwar.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29003.30243>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550150>

FIRST SECURITY ISLAMI BANK PLC.
Birulia Branch, Dhaka - (Routing No: 105260808)

Statement of Account

Customer ID : 0001308213	A/C No : 0178 1220003933
Name : MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	A/C Type : Mudarabah Savings Deposit Account
Address : CHARABAG (MADRASA MORE NORTH ROAD),ASULIA, SAVAR, DHAKA.	Currency : BDT
Proprietor :	A/C Status : REGULAR
City : SAVAR	A/C Open Date : 28-Aug-2017
Phone : 01788396264	
Period : 23/02/2016 TO 23/02/2025	Generation Date : 23-Feb-2025 2:24 pm

Date	Cheque No	Narration	Trans Type	Debit	Credit	Balance
Opening Balance						
28/08/2017		Cash	C GEN	0.00	500.13	500.13
10/09/2017		MICR Cheque Book Issue deducted.	T CHG	40.00	0.00	460.13
10/09/2017		VAT for MICR CHEQUE deducted.	T CHG	6.00	0.00	454.13
10/10/2017		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : 13100000173, Amt : 33065 - CITY UNIVERSITY TO MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	T GEN	0.00	33,065.00	33,519.13
ONLINE						
22/10/2017	1436391	MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	C GEN	13,000.00	0.00	20,519.13
02/11/2017	1436392	shajall	C GEN	5,000.00	0.00	15,519.13
05/11/2017		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : 90209157036, Amt : 25000 - salary of the month of Oct'2017	T GEN	0.00	25,000.00	40,519.13
ONLINE						
12/11/2017	1436393	Self	C GEN	5,000.00	0.00	35,519.13
22/11/2017	1436394	self	C GEN	10,000.00	0.00	25,519.13
28/11/2017	1436395	self	C GEN	20,000.00	0.00	5,519.13
06/12/2017		BFT: Salary for the month of November' 2017	T GEN	0.00	25,000.00	30,519.13
ONLINE						
19/12/2017	1436396	self	C GEN	30,000.00	0.00	519.13
26/12/2017		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2017. Q4	T CHG	57.50	0.00	461.63
30/12/2017		Profit on credit balance	T PFT	0.00	3.23	464.86
30/12/2017		10% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted.	T CHG	0.32	0.00	464.54
30/12/2017		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/07/2017 TO 30/12/2017	T CHG	100.00	0.00	364.54
30/12/2017		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/07/2017 TO 30/12/2017	T CHG	15.00	0.00	349.54
07/01/2018		BFT: CITY UNIVERSITY SALARY FOR THE MONTH OF DECEMBER'2017	T GEN	0.00	25,000.00	25,349.54
ONLINE						
08/01/2018	1436397	Self	C GEN	24,000.00	0.00	1,349.54
07/02/2018		BFT: CITY UNIVERSITY SALARY FOR THE MONTH OF JANUARY' 2018	T GEN	0.00	25,000.00	26,349.54
ONLINE						
18/02/2018	1436398	Self	C GEN	25,000.00	0.00	1,349.54
07/03/2018		BFT: CITY UNIVERSITY SALARY FOR THE MONTH OF FEBRUARY' 2018	T GEN	0.00	25,000.00	26,349.54
ONLINE						
07/03/2018	1436399	self	C GEN	20,000.00	0.00	6,349.54
20/03/2018	1436400	self	C GEN	6,000.00	0.00	349.54
25/03/2018		MICR Cheque Book Issue deducted.	T CHG	40.00	0.00	309.54
25/03/2018		VAT for MICR CHEQUE deducted.	T CHG	6.00	0.00	303.54

C= Cash, T= Transfer, L= Clearing

THIS IS A COMPUTER GENERATED STATEMENT AND REQUIRES NO SIGNATURE. IN CASE OF ANY DISCREPANCY IS FOUND, PLEASE BRING IT TO YOUR
BRANCH MANAGER'S NOTICE WITHIN 15 DAYS OF RECEIPT OF THIS STATEMENT. OTHERWISE THIS STATEMENT WILL BE CONSIDERED CORRECT.

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Customer ID : 0001308213	A/C No : 0178 12200003933
Name : MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	A/C Type : Mudarabah Savings Deposit Account
Address : CHARABAG (MADRASA MORE NORTH ROAD),ASULIA, SAVAR, DHAKA.	Currency : BDT
Proprietor :	A/C Status : REGULAR
City : SAVAR	A/C Open Date : 28-Aug-2017
Phone : 01788396264	:
Period : 23/02/2016 TO 23/02/2025	Generation Date : 23-Feb-2025 2:24 pm

Date	Cheque No	Narration	Trans Type	Debit	Credit	Balance
28/03/2018		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2018.Q1	T	CHG 86.25	0.00	217.29
08/04/2018		BFT:CITY UNIVERSITY SALARY FOR THE MONTH OF FEBRUARY' 2018	T	GEN 0.00	25,000.00	25,217.29
09/04/2018	3163192	self	C	GEN 24,000.00	0.00	1,217.29
08/05/2018		BFT:City University salary fo the month of April' 2018	T	GEN 0.00	25,000.00	26,217.29
03/06/2018	3163193	self	C	GEN 25,000.00	0.00	1,217.29
06/06/2018		BFT:City University salary fo the month of May' 2018	T	GEN 0.00	25,000.00	26,217.29
19/06/2018		Profit transferred from 0178:24400000070	T	GEN 0.00	1,518.75	27,736.04
25/06/2018		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2018.Q2	T	CHG 86.25	0.00	27,649.79
30/06/2018		Profit on credit balance	T	PFT 0.00	4.19	27,653.98
30/06/2018		10% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted.	T	CHG 0.42	0.00	27,653.56
30/06/2018		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/01/2018 TO 30/06/2018	T	CHG 300.00	0.00	27,353.56
30/06/2018		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/01/2018 TO 30/06/2018	T	CHG 45.00	0.00	27,308.56
08/07/2018		BFT:City University salary fo the month of June' 2018	T	GEN 0.00	25,000.00	52,308.56
09/07/2018		Principal Transferred From 0178 - 24400000070	T	GEN 0.00	50,000.00	102,308.56
09/07/2018	3163194	Self	C	GEN 102,000.00	0.00	308.56
09/07/2018		Cash	C	GEN 0.00	200.00	508.56
07/08/2018		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : 90209157036, Amt : 25000 - SALARY FOR THE MONTH OF JULY 2018	T	GEN 0.00	25,000.00	25,508.56
12/08/2018		BFT:Honorarium payment of Summer 2017	T	GEN 0.00	10,400.00	35,908.56
14/08/2018		BFT:Honorarium payment of Spring 2018	T	GEN 0.00	15,000.00	50,908.56
29/08/2018		Recalculated Excess Profit Applied to Client	T	PFT 0.00	0.01	50,908.57
04/09/2018	3163195	self	C	GEN 25,000.00	0.00	25,908.57
06/09/2018		BFT:Salary Month of August-2018	T	GEN 0.00	25,000.00	50,908.57
24/09/2018		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2018.Q3	T	CHG 86.25	0.00	50,822.32
03/10/2018	3163196	Self	C	GEN 10,000.00	0.00	40,822.32

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 16 June 2025.

FIRST SECURITY ISLAMI BANK PLC.
Birulia Branch, Dhaka - (Routing No: 105260808)

Statement of Account

Customer ID : 0001308213	A/C No : 0178 1220003933
Name : MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	A/C Type : Mudarabah Savings Deposit Account
Address : CHARABAG (MADRASA MORE NORTH ROAD),ASULIA, SAVAR, DHAKA.	Currency : BDT
Proprietor :	A/C Status : REGULAR
City : SAVAR	A/C Open Date : 28-Aug-2017
Phone : 01788396264	:
Period : 23/02/2016 TO 23/02/2025	Generation Date : 23-Feb-2025 2:24 pm

Date	Cheque No	Narration	Trans Type	Debit	Credit	Balance
07/10/2018		BFT:Salary Month of September-2018	T GEN	0.00	24,200.00	65,022.32
			ONLINE			
09/10/2018		MICR Cheque Book Issue deducted.	T CHG	40.00	0.00	64,982.32
09/10/2018		VAT for MICR CHEQUE deducted.	T CHG	6.00	0.00	64,976.32
07/11/2018		BFT:Salary Month of October-2018	T GEN	0.00	23,200.00	88,176.32
			ONLINE			
02/12/2018	3163197	MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	C GEN	10,000.00	0.00	78,176.32
06/12/2018	3163198	Self	C GEN	77,500.00	0.00	676.32
06/12/2018		BFT:Salary Month of November-2018	T GEN	0.00	25,000.00	25,676.32
			ONLINE			
18/12/2018		BFT[1]:Charge Debited for NID Verification	T GEN	2.30	0.00	25,674.02
24/12/2018		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2018.Q4	T CHG	86.25	0.00	25,587.77
27/12/2018		Profit on credit balance	T PFT	0.00	314.07	25,901.84
27/12/2018		10% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted.	T CHG	31.41	0.00	25,870.43
27/12/2018		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/07/2018 TO 27/12/2018	T CHG	300.00	0.00	25,570.43
27/12/2018		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/07/2018 TO 27/12/2018	T CHG	45.00	0.00	25,525.43
07/01/2019		BFT:Salary Month of December-2018	T GEN	0.00	25,000.00	50,525.43
			ONLINE			
07/01/2019		BFT:Internship and project bill for fall-2017	T GEN	0.00	3,900.00	54,425.43
			ONLINE			
07/01/2019		BFT:Lecturer honorarium of summer-2018	T GEN	0.00	15,000.00	69,425.43
			ONLINE			
07/01/2019	3163199	Self	C GEN	25,000.00	0.00	44,425.43
05/02/2019	3163200	self	C GEN	20,000.00	0.00	24,425.43
06/02/2019		BFT:Salary Month of January-2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	51,925.43
			ONLINE			
13/02/2019	4796311	self	C GEN	51,000.00	0.00	925.43
07/03/2019		BFT:Salary Month of February-2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	28,425.43
			ONLINE			
10/03/2019	3163191	Self	C GEN	25,000.00	0.00	3,425.43
28/03/2019		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2019.Q1	T CHG	86.25	0.00	3,339.18
02/04/2019	4796312	Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : , Cheque No. : -4796312 - self	T GEN	2,500.00	0.00	839.18
			ONLINE			
07/04/2019		BFT:Salary Month of March-2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	28,339.18
			ONLINE			
07/04/2019		BFT:Internship & Project bill For the semester of Spring '2018	T GEN	0.00	6,500.00	34,839.18
			ONLINE			
08/04/2019	4796313	Self	C GEN	22,000.00	0.00	12,839.18
23/04/2019	4796314	Self	C GEN	12,000.00	0.00	839.18

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Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
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 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design PLC, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite PLC, Radix PLC, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar, Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

FIRST SECURITY ISLAMI BANK PLC.
Birulia Branch, Dhaka - (Routing No: 105260808)

Statement of Account

Customer ID : 0001308213	A/C No : 0178 12200003933
Name : MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	A/C Type : Mudarabah Savings Deposit Account
Address : CHARABAG (MADRASA MORE NORTH ROAD),ASULIA, SAVAR, DHAKA.	Currency : BDT
Proprietor : SAVAR	A/C Status : REGULAR
City : SAVAR	A/C Open Date : 28-Aug-2017
Phone : 01788396264	
Period : 23/02/2016 TO 23/02/2025	Generation Date : 23-Feb-2025 2:24 pm

Date	Cheque No	Narration	Trans Type	Debit	Credit	Balance
29/04/2019		BFT:Lecturer Honorarium for the period of Fall '2018	T GEN	0.00	15,000.00	15,839.18
06/05/2019		BFT:Salary Month of April-2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	43,339.18
07/05/2019	4796315	self	C GEN	39,000.00	0.00	4,339.18
27/05/2019		BFT:Eid-UI-Fitre Bonus-2019	T GEN	0.00	11,344.00	15,683.18
27/05/2019		BFT:Salary Month of May-2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	43,183.18
30/05/2019	4796316	self	C GEN	10,000.00	0.00	33,183.18
09/06/2019		MICR Cheque Book Issue deducted.	T CHG	50.00	0.00	33,133.18
09/06/2019		VAT for MICR CHEQUE deducted.	T CHG	7.50	0.00	33,125.68
09/06/2019		MICR Cheque Book Issue deducted.	T CHG	50.00	0.00	33,075.68
09/06/2019		VAT for MICR CHEQUE deducted.	T CHG	7.50	0.00	33,068.18
18/06/2019	4796317	self	C GEN	25,000.00	0.00	8,068.18
26/06/2019		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2019.Q2	T CHG	86.25	0.00	7,981.93
30/06/2019		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/01/2019 TO 30/06/2019	T CHG	300.00	0.00	7,681.93
30/06/2019		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/01/2019 TO 30/06/2019	T CHG	45.00	0.00	7,636.93
07/07/2019		BFT:Salary Month of June-2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	35,136.93
08/07/2019	4796319	self	C GEN	34,500.00	0.00	636.93
29/07/2019		Recalculated Excess Profit Applied to Client	T PFT	0.00	1.35	638.28
29/07/2019		10% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted. 0	T CHG	0.14	0.00	638.14
06/08/2019		BFT: Salary Month of July-2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	28,138.14
06/08/2019		BFT: Festival Bonus Month of July-2019	T GEN	0.00	11,344.00	39,482.14
08/08/2019	4796318	Self	C GEN	38,500.00	0.00	982.14
03/09/2019		BFT:Internship & Project bill for Summer '2018 (Fund Transfer)	T GEN	0.00	5,200.00	6,182.14
03/09/2019		BFT:Lecturer Honorarium of Spring '2019 (Fund Transfer)	T GEN	0.00	15,000.00	21,182.14
05/09/2019		BFT:Salary For the month of August '2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	48,682.14
08/09/2019	4796320	self	C GEN	48,000.00	0.00	682.14
26/09/2019		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2019.Q2	T CHG	86.25	0.00	595.89

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FIRST SECURITY ISLAMI BANK PLC.
Birulia Branch, Dhaka - (Routing No: 105260808)

Statement of Account

Customer ID : 0001308213	A/C No : 0178 1220003933
Name : MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	A/C Type : Mudarabah Savings Deposit Account
Address : CHARABAG (MADRASA MORE NORTH ROAD),ASULIA, SAVAR, DHAKA.	Currency : BDT
Proprietor :	A/C Status : REGULAR
City :SAVAR	A/C Open Date : 28-Aug-2017
Phone :01788396264	
Period :23/02/2016 TO 23/02/2025	Generation Date : 23-Feb-2025 2:24 pm

Date	Cheque No	Narration	Trans Type	Debit	Credit	Balance
06/10/2019		BFT:Salary For the month of September '2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	28,095.89
			ONLINE			
06/10/2019	5636021	Self	C GEN	25,000.00	0.00	3,095.89
07/11/2019		BFT:Salary For the month of October '2019	T GEN	0.00	26,700.00	29,795.89
			ONLINE			
11/11/2019	5636022	Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : , Cheque No. : -5636022 - SELF	T GEN	25,000.00	0.00	4,795.89
			ONLINE			
14/11/2019		SELF	C GEN	0.00	100,000.00	104,795.89
18/11/2019		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : , Amt : 100000 - cash	T GEN	0.00	100,000.00	204,795.89
			ONLINE			
18/11/2019		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI, Rem A/c : , Chg/Vat Coll. - cashcash	T CHG	57.50	0.00	204,738.39
			ONLINE			
21/11/2019		solveny certificate charge and VAT.	T GEN	575.00	0.00	204,163.39
25/11/2019	5636023	self	C GEN	25,000.00	0.00	179,163.39
05/12/2019		BFT:Salary for the m/o November'2019	T GEN	0.00	27,500.00	206,663.39
			ONLINE			
10/12/2019		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : , Amt : 100000 - cash	T GEN	0.00	100,000.00	306,663.39
			ONLINE			
10/12/2019		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI, Rem A/c : , Chg/Vat Coll. - cashcash	T CHG	57.50	0.00	306,605.89
			ONLINE			
22/12/2019		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2019.Q4	T CHG	86.25	0.00	306,519.64
26/12/2019		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/07/2019 TO 26/12/2019	T CHG	200.00	0.00	306,319.64
26/12/2019		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/07/2019 TO 26/12/2019	T CHG	30.00	0.00	306,289.64
26/12/2019		Excise Duty on Deposit FROM 01/01/2019 TO 26/12/2019	T CHG	150.00	0.00	306,139.64
29/12/2019	5636024	SELF	C GEN	35,000.00	0.00	271,139.64
30/12/2019		Profit on credit balance	T PFT	0.00	539.98	271,679.62
30/12/2019		15% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted.	T CHG	81.00	0.00	271,598.62
07/01/2020		BFT:Salary For the month of December '2019	T GEN	0.00	25,700.00	297,298.62
			ONLINE			
14/01/2020	5636025	Rem Br : 0115-BANANI(O), Rem A/c : , Local Cheque No. : -5636025 - SELF	T GEN	55,000.00	0.00	242,298.62
			ONLINE			
14/01/2020		Rem Br : 0115-BANANI, Rem A/c : , Chg/Vat Coll. - SELFSELF	T CHG	57.50	0.00	242,241.12
			ONLINE			

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

FIRST SECURITY ISLAMI BANK PLC.
Birulia Branch, Dhaka - (Routing No: 105260808)

Statement of Account

Customer ID : 0001308213	A/C No : 0178 12200003933
Name : MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN	A/C Type : Mudarabah Savings Deposit Account
Address : CHARABAG (MADRASA MORE NORTH ROAD),ASULIA, SAVAR, DHAKA.	Currency : BDT
Proprietor :	A/C Status : REGULAR
City : SAVAR	A/C Open Date : 28-Aug-2017
Phone : 01788396264	
Period : 23/02/2016 TO 23/02/2025	Generation Date : 23-Feb-2025 2:24 pm

Date	Cheque No	Narration	Trans Type	Debit	Credit	Balance
22/01/2020	5636026	SELF	C	20,000.00	0.00	222,241.12
26/01/2020	5636027	BANK ASIA LTD.,RV,5636027	T	217,600.00	0.00	4,641.12
28/01/2020	5636028	Self	C	4,100.00	0.00	541.12
06/02/2020		BFT:Salary For the month of January '2020	T	0.00	30,300.00	30,841.12
					ONLINE	
13/02/2020		BFT:LECTURER HONORARIUM PAYMENT FOR SUMMER'2019 & FALL'2019	T	0.00	15,000.00	45,841.12
					ONLINE	
18/02/2020	5636029	Rem Br : 0253-TANG(O), Rem A/c : , Local Cheque No. : -5636029 - PAID TO MD.JAHANGIR HOSSAIN	T	25,000.00	0.00	20,841.12
					ONLINE	
29/03/2020		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2020.Q1	T	115.00	0.00	20,726.12
24/06/2020		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2020.Q2	T	115.00	0.00	20,611.12
25/06/2020		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/01/2020 TO 25/06/2020	T	200.00	0.00	20,411.12
25/06/2020		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/01/2020 TO 25/06/2020	T	30.00	0.00	20,381.12
30/06/2020		Profit on credit balance	T	0.00	244.83	20,625.95
30/06/2020		10% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted.	T	24.48	0.00	20,601.47
31/08/2020		Recalculated Excess Profit Applied to Client	T	0.00	3.86	20,605.33
31/08/2020		10% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted. 0	T	0.39	0.00	20,604.94
24/09/2020		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2020.Q2	T	115.00	0.00	20,489.94
24/12/2020		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/07/2020 TO 31/12/2020	T	100.00	0.00	20,389.94
24/12/2020		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/07/2020 TO 31/12/2020	T	15.00	0.00	20,374.94
27/12/2020		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2020.Q4	T	115.00	0.00	20,259.94
30/12/2020		Profit on credit balance	T	0.00	323.03	20,582.97
30/12/2020		10% Source Tax on Profit on Deposit deducted.	T	32.30	0.00	20,550.67
30/12/2020		Excise Duty on Deposit FROM 01/01/2020 TO 31/12/2020	T	150.00	0.00	20,400.67
28/03/2021		Charge and VAT on SMS Service Realized for the year 2021.Q1	T	115.00	0.00	20,285.67
24/06/2021		Account Maintenance Fee for MSD FROM 01/01/2021 TO 30/06/2021	T	100.00	0.00	20,185.67
24/06/2021		VAT on Account Maintenance Charge on MSD FROM 01/01/2021 TO 30/06/2021	T	15.00	0.00	20,170.67

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